

RIGOUROUS

secuRe desIGn and deploYment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

[Deliverable 2.3]

FINAL RIGOUROUS REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

Title	Final RIGOUROUS Reference Architecture
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Table 1: List of abbreviations and acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	Artificial Intelligence as a Service
AID	AI-driven Decision Engine
AIRM	AI-driven 6G Response-Mitigation
AOUI	Application Onboarding User Interface
B5G	Beyond 5G
BOM	Bootstrapping and Onboarding Management
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CSRIT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CTI	Cyber Threat Intelligence
DevOps	Development, Operations

DevPrivOps	Development, Privacy aware Operations
DevSecOps	Development, Security, Operations
DCC	Design Requirement
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DoS	Denial of Service
DS	Data Services
DSC	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition
DT	Digital Twin
EAP-TLS	Extensible Authentication Protocol-Transport Layer Security
EDoS	Economical Denial of Sustainability
FB	Functional block
FL	Federated learning
HLA	High Level Architecture
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IOC	Indicators of Compromise
IMP	Implementation Requirement
INT	Interface Requirement
ISM	Intent-based Security Management
LEG	Legal Requirement
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MAPE-K	Monitor-Analyse -Plan-Execute plus Knowledge
ML	Machine Learning
MRACL	Model-Reference Adaptive Control Loop
MTD	Moving Target Defence
NF	Network Function
NPN	Non-Public Network
NRF	Network Repository Function
OODA	Observe, Orient, Decide, Act

OPR	Operating Requirement
PET	Privacy-Enhancing Technologies
PNF	Physical Network Function
PUI	Human controllable Privacy User Interface
RM	Response Mitigation
RMUI	Response-Mitigation policies
SA	Security Agent
SAE	Security Analytics Engine
SC	Service Composition
SCUI	Service Composition User Interface
SDN	Software Defined Network
SEC	Security Requirement
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SM	Slide Management
SMD	Security Management domains
SO	Security Orchestrator
SOAR	Security Orchestration Automation Response
SOUI	Security Onboarding User Interface
STIX	Structured Threat Information eXpression
SUI	Security formal modelling User Interface
TESF	Trust evaluation and enabler service functionalities
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
UE	User Equipment
USA	Usability Requirement
VNF	Virtual Network Function
ZSM	Zero-Touch Network and Service Management
ZTM	Zero-Trust and Identity Management

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of this document is to describe the final version of the RIGOUROUS architecture, used as baseline in the project to deliver an intelligent, autonomous, and security management and orchestration framework for designing, developing, testing, and integrating next-generation services deployed over AI-driven 6G networks.

The architecture has been used as reference to develop the RIGOUROUS innovations and validate them in the use cases. The architecture follows a DevSecOps approach thereby including mechanisms for a model-driven automatic enforcement of security policies defined by administrators, software developers or security operators within the network. The architecture is inspired in a SOAR [5] vision that combines incident response, orchestration and automation, and threat intelligence management capabilities in a single solution to come up with a closed loop for multi-domain 6G security network management.

The Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) architecture [1] from ETSI describes a set of architectural principles for a zero-touch automated network and service management in a multi-vendor environment. Rigorous architecture adopt most of these principles and expands ZSM with a set of dedicated security functional components for cognitive security decision, security management, supporting closed-loop operation combined with a SOAR approach.

In addition, the architecture considers Zero Trust as defined by NIST.SP.800-207 [2], that trust is never granted implicitly but must be continually evaluated. The architecture features a trust service which can enable continuous trust validation (i.e., monitoring the state) and minimization of impacts (i.e., if any security breach occurs prevention of threat lateral movement), where the trust service considers various factors including behavioural/environmental attributes, monitoring/measuring the integrity or security posture of the involved function or entity.

The architecture relies on AI as a service where the architectural functional blocks are AI-driven and generate intelligent information and automation mechanisms in terms of making smart decisions, incident detection, orchestration, management and intelligent data monitoring by triggering security events-alerts.

This document presents the final version of the architecture, the general proactive and reactive flows and delves into the main process workflows involving the architectural components that are needed to accomplish the projects goals demanded in different tasks of work packages WP3 and WP4. Furthermore, the document updates the functional and non-functional requirements that were originally defined in D2.1, detailing better their scope and mapping to use cases and architectural components.

Finally, this document reviews the project's use cases definitions that were documented in deliverable D2.2. The document dedicates a section that updates part of the use cases with more realistic attacks scenarios and mitigations that are dynamically orchestrated in the network to counter ongoing attack.

2 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the final RIGOUROUS architecture, including the definition of the process

workflows considered across the functional components and definition of the main interfaces of the services. This can be considered the utmost contribution of Task T2.3 to Rigorous project. The architecture has been updated from the first version in D2.1 in order to reflect better the functionalities that are been implemented and/or envisioned to be delivered in technical work packages WP3 and WP4. In particular it defines process flows for:

- Onboarding, devsecops and devpriops
- Security orchestration and enforcement
- Zero trust
- 6g network slicing
- Ai-based anomaly detection
- Provided services
- Ai-based decision
- Risk assessment
- Automated service composition and digital twin
- Response and mitigation

In addition to that, the document updates the requirements definitions given more details in each of them and linking them better to RIGOUROUS assets and use cases. Finally, this document also recaps the updated version of the Use Cases that have been better described to include more realistic attacks and mitigations affecting Beyond 5G networks.

The present deliverable is structured into six major chapters, as follows:

- *Chapter 3* describes an updated version of the requirements definitions that were originally identified in deliverable D2.1. Both functional and non-functional requirements are reviewed, adding further details not detailed in D2.1 about the mapping to the use case and Rigorous assets.
- *Chapter 4* this section updates the use cases description, including more realistic attack scenarios and mitigation actions originally defined in D2.2.
- *Chapter 5* presents the final Rigorous Architecture design. This new version deeps into the concrete workflows between the functional components and subcomponents to carry out the main functionalities expected in the project.
- *Chapter 6* presents a mapping of Rigorous architecture to ETSI Zero touch network & Service Management (ZSM) and 3GPP technical reports.
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- *Chapter 7* presents the conclusions.

3 UPDATED LIST OF REQUIREMENTS

This section presents an updated version of the functional and non-functional requirements that provides greater detail in the definition of each requirement. This new version of requirements also provides mapping between the requirements, and the applicable components. In addition, this updated version provides a mapping between each UC functional and non-functional requirements to the relevant components of the RIGOUROUS platform.

3.1. List of functional requirements

RIGOUROUS' Requirements elicitation methodology, and the respective requirements engineering process, have been reported in D2.1 - "System Requirements Analysis Report" [18], in Section 3.

D2.3 re-iterates on the requirements definition in D2.1, to address the feedback received in the projects' first review process, specifically adding a detailed description for both, functional and non-functional requirements, a detailed mapping to the applicable components in the overall RIGOUROUS architecture, and a mapping to the Use-Cases, part of RIGOUROUS.

The "Details" Column, in Tables 4 and 5, lists the expanded context for the engineering, and elicitation of each requirement, while the "Applicable to component" and "Details of the mapping of the requirement to asset" columns, provides the mapping of each requirement to the respective component - "asset"- of RIGOUROUS.

ID	Name	Details (Expand from "Name")	Asset	Owner	Mappi ng to Use-Case #	Detail the mapping of the requirement to the asset
RIG_FUN_T3_1_010	The framework should support the traceability, storage and management of security/privacy policies, as well as the translation from policy models to specific domain element configurations	The framework should support the management storage of policies. It should be able to translate to configurations of diverse technologies such as virtual firewalls, IDS, MANO, Controllers.	ISM	UMU	UC1, UC2, UC3	The requirement is related to the ISM (intent-based security Manager) in charge of translating policies.
RIG_FUN_T3_1_020	The Intent-Based Security Management component should support different security policies and be able to detect conflicts among policies	The framework should support the management of diverse kind of security and privacy policies, including Federated Learning policies, Filtering Policies, Channel Protection Policies, IDS policies, Network slicing, Monitoring policies, command and control	ISM	UMU	UC, UC2, UC3	The requirement is related to the ISM (intent-based security Manager) in charge of detect conflicts

RIG_FUN_T3_2_030	The AI-Driven Security Orchestrator should be driven by interoperable intents or policy models	The Orchestrator should use the policies for automatic enforcement configuration of VNFs, using extensible orchestration enforcement, supporting diverse NFV, SDN controllers and security agents. the orchestration should support different algorithms to decide the best allocation for a security enforcement.	SO	UMU	UC, UC2, UC3	This requirement maps to the Security orchestrator that implement this functionality
RIG_FUN_T3_3_040	The access control functions (e.g., network repository function) shall enforce access control (i.e., service consumption and provision) in accordance with the trust-based security policies.	The ZTM functional block has been implemented to calculate the trust score for it to be used in the RIGOUROUS framework to apply the necessary access control during the service orchestration.	ZTM	LNVO	UC1	The requirement is related to the ZTM specific asset - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification
RIG_FUN_T3_3_050	The Trust evaluation and enabler service function shall analyse and determine if there exists any attack trace in the collected data and provide trust data that includes cause code, configuration issues, malfunction alerts, trust	The ZTM functional block has been implemented to take attack detection input into account to calculate the trust score for it to be used in the RIGOUROUS framework to apply the necessary access control during the service orchestration.	ZTM	LNVO	UC1	The requirement is related to the ZTM specific asset - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification

	value(s), recommended actions and timestamp.					
RIG_FUN_T3.3_060	The Policy control function shall create security policies based on the trust data and notify to the access control functions	The ZTM functional block has been implemented to calculate the trust score for it to be used in the RIGOUROUS framework to create security policies and to apply the necessary access control during the service orchestration.	ZTM	LNVO	UC1	The requirement is related to the ZTM specific asset - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification
RIG_FUN_T3.3_070	The system shall perform security monitoring and trust evaluation using one or more Trust evaluation and enabler service function(s)	The ZTM functional block has been implemented to calculate the trust score for it to be used in the RIGOUROUS framework to apply the necessary access control during the service orchestration.	ZTM	LNVO	UC1	The requirement is related to the ZTM specific asset - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification
RIG_FUN_T3.4_080	The system shall have the capability to assign specific application related traffic over their correct slice, such as	The system shall classify and route application traffic to the appropriate network slice based on bandwidth, availability, priority, and security policies. It shall enforce isolation, prevent unauthorized access, and adapt to real-time network conditions. Security mechanisms, including	SM, RM	ONE	UC1	This requirement is the main responsibility of the SM component.

	expected bandwidth, availability or priority	anomaly detection and logging, shall be integrated to monitor and mitigate potential threats.				
RIG_FUN_T41_090	The Security Analytics Engine should leverage Federated Learning along with Privacy-Enhancing Technologies in the model training phase to prevent information leaks during its lifecycle	The Security Analytics should be implemented with different techniques such as Differential privacy or homomorphic encryption	SAE	OULU	UC2/UC4	RIG_FUN_T41_090 maps to Security Analytics Engine functional block, demonstrating the feasibility of integrating various Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) to empower privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detection.
RIG_FUN_T41_100	The RIGOUROUS framework should allow users to create privacy policies and to make configurations using a graphical user interface	The PUI shall enable users to define privacy policies and the SMUI to define other types of configurations and policies (namely, security) affecting services	PUI, SMUI	ITAV	UC4	This requirement is mapped to the PUI and SMUI
			CTI	UMU	UC1	

RIG_FUN_T4 1_110	The Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing should be able to post the obfuscated events on the requester organization's Threat Intelligence Platform instance	The privacy-preserving techniques for protecting CTI sharing should be defined based on user policies				This map to the pp-CTI functional component of the architecture, aimed to obfuscate the CTI information prior sharing
RIG_FUN_T4 1_120	The Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing should be able to retrieve events published on the organization TIP and received from other organizations, from a timestamp provided	The pp-CTI sharing middleware should support different obfuscation techniques	CTI	UMU	UC1	This map to the pp-CTI functional component of the architecture, aimed to obfuscate the CTI information prior sharing
RIG_FUN_T4 .1_130	The RIGOUROUS framework can provide controlling over involved parameters e.g., the batch size involved in training, the participation of devices in federated learning rounds, to optimize the learning process	The RIGOUROUS framework can provide controlling over involved parameters e.g., the batch size involved in training, the participation of devices in federated learning rounds, to optimize the learning process. The federated training process should lead to a model that can accurately detect network anomalies based on the collected network traffic, while striking the balance between model performances (i.e., anomaly detection accuracy)	SAE	OULU/I CT-FI	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_130 maps to the Security Analytics Engine functional block, defining the federated training parameters that allow to build effective anomaly detection models

		and convergence (i.e., time needed to finish the training).				in a collaborative way.
RIG_FUN_T4.1_140	The Response Mitigation component should be capable of reducing the damage incurred by stealthy attacks such as DDoS or/and EDoS attacks	The Response Mitigation component should be capable of reducing the damage incurred by stealthy attacks such as DDoS and EDoS attacks. Based on the data collected on the resource usage and performance metrics of the services under monitoring, the Response Mitigation component should be capable of detecting anomalies in these metrics to prevent malicious requests for scaling resources of the target service.	RM	OULU	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_140 maps to Response and Mitigation functional block, providing a service to mitigate economic losses and potential performance degradation by preventing malicious exploitation of auto-scaling capability.
			AID	EBOS		

RIG_FUN_T4 .1_150	the need for an enforcement engine for the mitigation action	integration with security orchestrator from UMU that needs to be implemented on each of the monitored infrastructure and enforce the mitigation action suggested by AID through the MSPL			All UCs in which R12 and CPC assets exist	this requirement is mapped to the AID and SO (security orchestrator)
RIG_FUN_T4 .1_160	The 6G Response Mitigation Functional block should be activated based on the AID-decision and type of Threat detected to apply the corresponding Threat Response and Mitigation	this is the internal functionality between the AID and the AI-RM, where the latter is triggered once the AID collect all the needed information needed for ML algorithm in order to run the needed iterations and generate the optimum mitigation action	AID	EBOS	All UCs in which R12 and CPC assets exist	this requirement is mapped to the AID, as internal function
RIG_FUN_T4 1_170	The use of the Threat Intelligence platform should only be available to authorized users, with permissions, previously registered in the domain	Only authorized users should be able to access to the CTI platform to obfuscated events	CTI	UMU	UC1	This map to the pp-CTI functional component of the architecture, aimed to obfuscate the CTI information prior sharing
			SAE	ICT-FI	UC2	

RIG_FUN_T4.1_180	The RIGOUROUS framework should be capable of delivering high responsiveness by reducing the time required by encryption/decryption operations	The RIGOUROUS framework should be designed to achieve high responsiveness by optimizing encryption and decryption operations. This involves offloading operational overhead and localizing the encryption and decryption processes to reduce transport delays. Additionally, the framework should dynamically adjust encryption parameters based on system security requirements, ensuring a balance between data protection and processing speed.				RIG_FUN_T4.1_180 maps to the Encryption/Decryption Operations functional block, demonstrating its role in serving cryptographic services efficiently and securely.
RIG_FUN_T4.1_190	The AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine should allow improving the anomaly detection accuracy by leveraging the knowledge transfer enabled by federated learning	The AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine should allow improving the anomaly detection accuracy by leveraging the knowledge transfer enabled by federated learning. The trained model should enable increased accuracy in identifying malicious network traffic, generating anomaly reports with details on the malicious traffic (e.g., IP source & port) that allow them to generate mitigation policies (e.g., blocking traffic from the malicious source).	SAE	OULU/ICT-FI	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_190 maps to Security Analytics Engine functional block, demonstrating the advantage of using collaborative learning to improve anomaly detection while preserving data privacy.
			SAE	OULU	UC4	

RIG_FUN_T4.1_200	The Security Analytics Engine component should be capable of proactively withstanding adversarial attacks and increase the resilience of the ML models to them	The Security Analytics Engine component should be capable of proactively withstanding adversarial attacks and increase the resilience of the ML models to them. The proactive strategy should allow dynamic change of the attack surface over time to increase the adversary's uncertainty. One potential adversarial attack to consider is the poisoning attack against federated learning, allowing to build robust FL-based anomaly detection models.				RIG_FUN_T4.1_200 maps to Security Analytics Engine functional block, providing an MTD-based Robust AI service that leverages Moving Target Defense (MTD) paradigm to proactively protect ML models against adversarial attacks.
RIG_FUN_T4.2_210	Digital Twin should provide the Dynamic Automated Service Composition with a simulated model of different components that interact with each other.	Before or after applying any new configurations, the DT should be able to run a simulation, so as to support the DSC to detect interoperability mismatches (e.g., protocol mismatches and vulnerabilities, incompatible data formats, misconfigurations) that can lead to security threats.	DT	WINGS	UC3	RIG_FUN_T4.2_210 maps to Digital Twin, emphasizing its capability to simulate components and the data flow among them, so as to support the detection of

						interoperability mismatches and associated security threats and in general to contribute to the security evaluation/testing of the data flow among the components.
RIG_FUN_T4.2_220	Dynamic Automated Service Composition should analyse the failures that occur between the different components of the model	DSC should detect any interoperability conflicts that can lead to security threats, such as 1) Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities require adapters or converters, which can introduce security loopholes, 2) Incompatible data formats can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data, 3) Organizations may struggle to enforce uniform security policies across diverse systems, leading to misconfigurations.	DSC	WINGS	UC3	RIG_FUN_T4.2_220 maps to Dynamic Automated Service Composition, emphasizing its capability to detect interoperability mismatches and associated security threats in the data flow among the components.

RIG_FUN_T4.2_230	Dynamic automated service composition should provide solutions to resolve interconnection failures through reconfiguration of one or both components and their interfaces	DSC should resolve any interoperability conflicts that can lead to security threats, such as 1) Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities require adapters or converters, which can introduce security loopholes, 2) Incompatible data formats can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data, 3) Organizations may struggle to enforce uniform security policies across diverse systems, leading to misconfigurations.	DSC	WINGS	UC3	RIG_FUN_T4.2_230 maps to Dynamic Automated Service Composition, emphasizing its capability to resolve/repair interoperability mismatches and associated security threats in the data flow among the components.
RIG_FUN_T4.3_240	The Threat Risk Assessor shall perform threat risk analytics in accordance with the ZSM General Security Aspects	The TRA shall assess anomalies related to assets within the network system model - information that should be provided by the RIGOUROUS fabric at runtime. Then the TRA will evaluate their potential impact on system security and integrity - in accordance with the ZSM. The risk score will be determined based on Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) associated with these assets, providing a quantified measure of risk.	TRA	Starion	UC1 UC3 UC4	RIG_FUN_T4.3_240 relates to the TRA's capability to perform threat risk analytics in accordance with ZSM General Security Aspects. It assesses threats, vulnerabilities,

						and impacted assets using a structured approach aligned with industry standards such as NIST 800-30, and ITU-T X.805.
RIG_FUN_T4.3_250	The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) shall recognise and perform the classification using the ZSM assets categories defined in ZSM General Security Aspects	The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) shall focus on identifying and correlating assets within the ZSM system model to establish a coherent and logical attack path. By understanding the relationships and interdependencies between different assets within the Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) framework, the TRA will be able to map potential attack vectors, determining how threats could traverse through the system.	TRA	Starion	UC1 UC3 UC4	RIG_FUN_T4.3_250 relates to the TRA's ability to recognize and classify ZSM assets by assessing and categorizing assets within the system model based on predefined ZSM asset categories. This enables accurate threat correlation and the construction of logical attack paths.

RIG_FUN_T4.3_260	The platform should be able to identify patterns in data, transmitted by sensors and IoT devices, and detect anomalous instances	The Cyber physical correlator (CPC) as component of SAE should detect cyber-physical threats in real-time, such as a) Malicious unauthorized users infiltrating secure systems and access sensitive data, b) Continuous distributed DoS attacks disrupt network availability and system performance, by analysing the network traffic flow from devices and gateways.	SAE	WINGS	UC3	RIG_FUN_T4.3_260 maps to Cyber physical correlator (CPC) as component of SAE , emphasizing its capability to detect cyber-physical threats, by analysing the network traffic flow from devices and gateways.
RIG_FUN_T43_270	The RIGOUROUS framework shall guarantee security between the network functions, the user and the application instances by using mandatory security mechanisms	The RIGOUROUS framework shall enforce strict security between network functions, users, and application instances through mandatory security mechanisms. It shall implement authentication, encryption, and access control to prevent unauthorized interactions. Continuous monitoring and anomaly detection shall ensure threat resilience, safeguarding data integrity, confidentiality, and service reliability under varying operational conditions.	RM	ONE	All UCs	RIG_FUN_T43_270 relates to the framework capabilities into ensuring the proper policy enforcement, authorization and authentication mechanisms.
RIG_FUN_T4.3_280	The Threat Risk Assessor shall provide a qualitative	Qualitative risk scoring will classify risks using a binary approach, categorizing them as either "acceptable" or "not acceptable" based on the	TRA	Starion	UC1 UC3 UC4	RIG_FUN_T4.3_280 relates to the TRA's capability

	or semi-Quantitative risk score	<p>combination of impact severity and threat likelihood.</p> <p>Semi-quantitative risk scoring will assign a numerical or scaled risk score by combining the criticality of the impact with the level of threat, categorizing risks into multiple levels such as advisory, caution, or warning, depending on the operational framework.</p>				<p>to provide a qualitative or semi-quantitative risk score by assessing the likelihood of a threat materializing and its potential impact. The TRA applies either a binary classification (acceptable/unacceptable risk) or a numerical risk score to support informed security decision-making.</p>
RIG_FUN_T4.3_290	The AID-decision making functional block should be driven by the R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	<p>based on the anomaly detector R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework</p> <p>the AID will run internal algorithms in order to generate a mitigation action (for the anomalies the AID would rely on the TRA score to cross check which one should be sent for mitigation action)</p>	AID	EBOS	UC4	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework

RIG_FUN_T4.3_300	The AID-decision making functional block should be driven by R12: Privacy preserving FL based Anomaly Detector	based on the anomaly detector R12: Privacy preserving FL based Anomaly Detector the AID will run internal algorithms in order to generate a mitigation action	AID	EBOS	UC2	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the R12: Privacy preserving FL based Anomaly Detector
RIG_FUN_T4.3_310	The AID-decision making functional block should be driven by R12: Privacy preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	based on the anomaly detector R12: Privacy preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection the AID will run internal algorithms in order to generate a mitigation action	AID	EBOS	UC4	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the R12: Privacy preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection
RIG_FUN_T4.3_320	The platform should be able to detect falsified data and anomalies in IoT devices, gateways, edge and cloud, when there is a data injection attack or unauthorized access, respectively.	The Cyber physical correlator (CPC) as component of SAE should detect cyber-physical threats in real-time, such as a) Malicious unauthorized users infiltrating secure systems and accessing sensitive data and b) Discrete injection attacks manipulate data integrity and affect system performance.	SAE	WINGS	UC3	RIG_FUN_T4.3_20 maps to Cyber physical correlator (CPC) as component of SAE , emphasizing its capability to detect cyber-physical threats, by analysing the network traffic

						flow from devices and gateways.
RIG_FUN_T4.4_330	The RIGOUROUS framework shall allow the review of the latest topology of the device where it is deployed.	The RIGOUROUS framework should be capable of detecting and reporting the real-time status of the deployed 5G/6G network topology, including the connections of various devices. This topology metadata should provide physical and virtual hosts, bridges, interfaces, and their interconnections. Consequently, the E2E path of devices across the network can be accurately mapped.	DS	UWS	UC1	RIG_FUN_T4.4_330 maps to the Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) asset introduced and validated in T4.4. The distribution of this component enables the topology discovery along 5G/6G network.
RIG_FUN_T51_340	The RIGOUROUS platform should collect events coming from existing external systems of the end-users	The RIGOUROUS platform should have in place, at run time, data collecting capabilities, to interface with industry-standard data logging and shipping interfaces, such as (but not limited to) RFC5424 - Syslog. This will support the ingestion of data, and collection of events from systems existing in the end-users infrastructures, such as SIEMs, Network Security Appliances such as Firewalls, IDS/IPS, Load Balancers etc.	SAE	ORO	UC1	RIG_FUN_T51_340 maps to the Security Analytics Engine functionality, to define the expected level of integration with State of The Art external systems

						in infrastructure, UC
RIG_FUN_T5.2_350	RIGOUROUS framework should be able to classify attacks and leverage emerging ML techniques such as Deep Learning, to dynamically assess on them, and decide the legitimacy or maliciousness of a scaling request	Through the leveraging of threat classification, the RIGOUROUS framework should gain the capability to dynamically assess the maliciousness of requests targeting the 6G network services scaling, such as the dynamic adaptation of slices configurations, and discern whether any given request is benign or malign in nature.	RM	ORO	UC1	In UC1, the implementation of RM will provide a continuous-loop risk assessment for threat conditions targeting the 6G infrastructure.
RIG_FUN_T5.2_360	The system shall keep track of the resources used and the load per function or application	The system should monitor and log resource utilization and load per function or application, ensuring real-time tracking for performance and security analysis. It shall support automated scaling based on load demands while preventing system bottlenecks, ensuring optimal resource allocation and maintaining stability under varying workloads.	DM	ONE	All UCs	RIG_FUN_T5.2_360 relates to the monitoring capabilities that the RIGOUROUS framework needs to provide, namely, to prevent system bottlenecks by performing

						preventive actions.
RIG_FUN_T5.3_370	The system shall be able to autonomously scale up and down NFs and applications based on observed load, to meet the desired response time.	The system shall autonomously scale network functions and applications based on real-time load analysis to maintain the desired response time. It should implement intelligent scaling mechanisms to optimize resource efficiency while preventing bottlenecks. Security controls ensure safe scaling, mitigating risks from overload, malicious exploitation, or unauthorized resource consumption.	SCUI, RM	ONE	All UCs	RIG_FUN_T5.3_370 maps to the autoscaling capabilities provided by the RIGOUROUS framework aiming to provide the best quality of service.
RIG_FUN_T5.3_380	The system must be capable to enforce different redundancy levels depending on service characteristics	The system should enforce adaptive redundancy levels based on service characteristics, prioritizing high availability for critical services. It shall dynamically adjust redundancy to ensure quality of service, minimizing latency and downtime. Security mechanisms shall prevent redundancy misuse, ensuring resilience against failures and attacks while maintaining optimal performance for essential operations.	SCUI, RM	ONE	UC4	RIG_FUN_T5.3_380 relates with the network traffic prioritization mechanisms offered by the RIGOUROUS framework, especially valuable for high demanding

						scenarios, such as those in PPDR events.
RIG_FUN_T5.3_390	The system shall be able to migrate existing traffic flows over the different instances of NFs and applications as function of the observed load	The system shall dynamically migrate traffic flows across network function and application instances based on real-time load conditions to optimize performance and prevent congestion. It shall ensure seamless transitions with minimal disruption, maintaining service continuity. Security mechanisms shall protect against unauthorized flow migration, ensuring integrity, reliability, and resilience against potential attacks or failures.	SM, RM	ONE	UC1	RIG_FUN_T5.3_390 maps to the network traffic routing capabilities offered by the RIGOUROUS framework, namely used for the isolation of malicious flows.
RIG_FUN_T4.3_400	Get the risk score from an external asset (TRA in this case)	The AID internal operation relies on the risk score that will be generated and shared by the TRA in order to prioritize the anomaly received (the risk scores should be provided in case of the anomalies detected and based on TRA score the AID sent actions to SO)	AID	EBOS	All Use cases where AID is involved	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the R16, the TRA
RIG_FUN_T4.3_410	The AID-decision making functional block should be driven by CPC asset	Based on the anomaly detector CPC, the AID will run internal algorithms in order to generate a mitigation action	AID	EBOS	UC where CPC (anoma	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the CPC asset

	(cyber correlator) physical				ly detecti on) is used	
RIG_FUN_T4.3_420	The AID-decision making functional block should be driven by ZTM, while the risk score is as well shared by ZTM (separate plane than the normal R12 and TRA case)	based on the anomaly detector for ZTM, the AID will run internal algorithms in order to generate a mitigation action	AID	EBOS	UC where ZTM is used	this requirement is mapped to the AID and the ZTM asset

3.2. Non-functional requirements

ID	Name	Details - Expand from "Name"Details (Expand from "Name")	Asset	Owner	Mapping to Use-Case #	Detail the mapping of the requirement to the asset
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RIG_SEC_T3.3_010	The system shall enable Trust evaluation and enabler service function to collect time logs generated by the Network inference data such as logs and reports that included abnormal event(s) from the devices or network functions, via the management function. An abnormal event can be related to (i) the predefined service message violations, and (ii) the number of received service messages exceeding a configured limit in a time	The Trust Evaluation and enabler service function shall be able to analyze the real time logs generated by the Network Functions like AMF, SMF etc., as a way of data collection for anomaly detection.	ZTM	LNVO	UC1	RIG_SEC_T3.3_010 maps to the asset Trust Evaluation and Enabler Service Function (TESF) developed in T3.3 that can collect the logs of the network function to detect anomalies and assign trust scores
RIG_SEC_T3.2_020	The end-device shall be able to identify and verify trusted applications installed on the device	The end-device should receive policies together with the application ID and genuine fingerprint so that it can identify rogue applications with the same application ID that want to make use of the (privileged) handling of the application traffic, defined in the policies.	AOUI, BOM	LNVO	UC1	RIG_SEC_T3.2_020 maps to the Trusted application onboarding in T3.2 where the received credential from the NANCY Issuer also contains an attribute of the applications the respective network wants to manage with URSP rules. This attribute is protected with the Issuer public key to

						prevent knowledge on the managed applications.
RIG_SEC_T3.2_030	The system shall be able to securely bootstrap the end-devices and onboard them with respective credentials for access authentication/authorization	The system shall be able to provide means that an end-device can connect to a default credential server for authentication in the onboarding network and then retrieves from a credential sever the long-term credentials for (re)connecting to the home system where the end-device can authenticate and gets authorized for subscribed services.	BOM	LNVO	UC1	RIG_SEC_T3.2_030 maps to the IoT device bootstrapping specification developed in T3.2 where the retrieved long-term credentials are realized as Attribute-Based Credentials (ABC) Verifiable Credentials, which act as the digital identity of the IoT device, allowing it to authenticate itself in untrusted sub-networks, access network applications, use 6G services, and even authenticate and connect directly with other devices in a device-to-device (D2D) interaction, as long as both devices trust the credential issuer.
RIG_SEC_T3.2_040	The end-device shall be able to identify and verify trusted	PLEASE CHECK: THIS SEEMS SAME REQUIREMENT AS ABOVE IN RIG_SEC_T3.2_020	BOM	LNVO		This is duplicated from 020, should be deleted, all subsequent entries should be

	applications installed on the device					re-numbered starting from 040
RIG_DCC_T31_050	The RIGOUROUS framework security policy models should be extensible and interoperable	The policies should be based on machine-readable and interpretable languages to facilitate the processing and translation to specific configurations and the detection of conflicts in policies.	ISM	UMU	Add UC reference	Add details
RIG_DCC_T4.4_060	The RIGOUROUS framework shall raise an alert, in near real time, with the extracted information of the networks/end-device relative to the malicious flow detected or identify cyber-attacks e.g., related to EDGE Computing infrastructures.	The RIGOUROUS framework should generate an alert upon detecting a network cyber threat, such as a DDoS attack. This alert should include, but is not limited to, extracted information about the network and end devices related to the detected malicious flow or identified cyberattacks, including those associated with EDGE computing infrastructures.	RMD	UWS	UC1	RIG_DCC_T4.4_060 maps to the Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM) asset introduced and validated in T4.4. This component enables the prompt and close to real time detection of malicious flows in 5G/6G environments.
RIG_DCC_T4.4_070	The Security Analytics Engine component shall extract the 5G/6G network information from the malicious flow detected.	Upon detecting a network cyber threat, such as a DDoS attack, the Security Analytics Engine should generate an alert and produce detailed metadata on the detected malicious 5G/6G flow. This metadata should include encapsulated IPs, protocols, and MAC addresses, along with an analysis of the identified attack. Furthermore, the detection process can be carried out using either a centralized or distributed approach	SAE	UWS	UC1	RIG_DCC_T4.4_070 maps to the Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM) asset introduced and validated in T4.4. This component enables the prompt and close to real time detection of malicious flows in 5G/6G environments.

		and is designed to integrate with EDGE computing infrastructures.				
RIG_OPR_T52_080	RIGOUROUS platform should be capable to establish the area in which an attacker can perform lateral movement and detail related processes affected	The RIGOUROUS framework should be capable of extracting the End-to-End (E2E) path of malicious network flows detected within the 5G/6G infrastructure. This capability enables the platform to identify whether an attacker is executing lateral movement and determine the new E2E path that requires mitigation.	SAE	UWS	UC1	RIG_OPR_T52_080 corresponds to the Slice Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS), which is responsible for correlating 5G/6G network topology and flow information to determine the E2E path of detected malicious flows. This asset is introduced and validated in T4.4.
RIG_IMP_T3.4_090	The Network Slicing component shall be agnostic of the technology and enforces the slicing rule	The Network Self-Protection (NSP) component shall enforce network slicing rules through an intent-based interface. This approach ensures agnosticism to the underlying data path technology, supporting mechanisms such as Linux Traffic Control (TC), Open vSwitch (OVS), and Iptables, among others.	SM	UWS	UC1	RIG_IMP_T3.4_090 directly maps to the NSP component, which is introduced and validated in T3.4. This component enforces network slicing rules in the 5G/6G data path and performs fine-grained classification of network packets.

RIG_OPR_T4.3_100	simultaneous decision making	the decision making from teh AID can process many anomalies received concurrently and for each propose the optimum mitigation	AID	EBOS	All UCs where AID is involved	RIG_AID_T4.3_100 maps to the capacity of the AID to process many anomalies
RIG_DCC_T3.1_110	The Onboarding Tools component shall identify high risk components before deployment	The Onboarding Tools enable modeling of the software before onboarding, and modeling of software driven policies to assess risk. Furthermore, risk score can be requested to the TRA, which computes a score based on the software's known vulnerabilities	PQ	ITAV	UC4	RIG_DCC_T3.1_110 directly maps to the operation of the onboarding tools Privacy Quantifier (PQ) and the capability for developers to define specific quality-based policies, which are integrated with dynamic information to produce a risk score
RIG_OPR_T3.1_120	The RIGOUROUS framework shall apply intrinsic mitigation strategies for network based attacks	The RIGOROUS framework shall enforce policies to enable services with specific enhanced network-based security characteristics for MTD at network level, effectively mitigating several network-based attacks	OT	ITAV	UC4	RIG_OPR_T3.1_120 directly maps to the operation of the onboarding tools NMTD and the capability for developers to define enhanced security characteristics, that affect the instantiation with hardening mechanisms.

RIG_OPR_T4.3_130	The RIGOUROUS framework shall implement retry mechanisms for failed requests to external services.	The RIGOUROUS framework shall implement retry mechanisms for failed requests to external services. In case of failed requests to internal services (e.g., CVE DB, System Model), the RIGOUROUS framework shall provide automatic backoff strategies/mechanisms to handle potential failures when making requests to such services. If the service remains unavailable after a predefined number of retry attempts, a warning shall be logged to notify system operators of the issue.	TRA	Starion	UC1, UC3, UC4	RIG_TRA_T4.3_130 maps to the TRA's ability to automatically handle external service request failures in a zero-touch architecture.
RIG_IMP_T4.3_140	The RIGOUROUS framework shall support more anomaly reports concurrently without degradation in performance.	The RIGOUROUS framework shall be designed to efficiently handle an increasing number of concurrent anomaly reports, ensuring that performance remains stable and responsive even under higher load conditions. To maintain system reliability, the framework shall optimize resource allocation and processing efficiency, preventing bottlenecks that could impact anomaly detection and risk assessment workflows.	TRA	Starion	UC1, UC3, UC4	RIG_TRA_T4.3_140 directly maps to the TRA's ability to handle a high volume of anomalies efficiently.

RIG_IMP_T4.1_15	RIGOUROUS framework should support different privacy-enhancing technologies	The RIGOUROUS framework should support the integration of multiple privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), including but not limited to homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, zero-knowledge proofs, and secure multi-party computation.	SAE	OULU	UC5	This requirement directly maps to the SAE's Privacy-Enhancing Service, allowing to enable privacy-preserving Federated Learning training process
RIG_OPR_T4.1_16	The RIGOUROUS framework can provide control over involved parameters in federated learning.	The RIGOUROUS framework enables control over parameters such as batch size and device participation in federated learning rounds to optimize the learning process. The training should result in a model that accurately detects network anomalies while balancing detection accuracy and convergence speed.	SAE	ICT-FI	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_130 maps to the Security Analytics Engine functional block, defining the federated training parameters for anomaly detection.
RIG_OPR_T4.1_17	The RIGOUROUS framework should be capable of delivering high responsiveness by reducing encryption/decryption time.	The RIGOUROUS framework optimizes encryption/decryption operations to reduce overhead and localize processing, minimizing transport delay. Additionally, it dynamically adjusts encryption parameters based on security needs, balancing data protection and processing speed.	SAE	ICT-FI	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_180 maps to the Encryption/Decryption Operations functional block, demonstrating its role in efficient cryptographic services.

RIG_OPR_T4.1_18	The AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine should enhance anomaly detection using federated learning.	The AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine improves anomaly detection accuracy through knowledge transfer in federated learning. The model enhances accuracy in identifying malicious network traffic and generates reports detailing anomalies (e.g., IP source, port) for mitigation policies.	SAE	ICT-FI	UC2	RIG_FUN_T4.1_190 maps to the Security Analytics Engine, showcasing the benefits of collaborative learning for anomaly detection.
RIG_OPR_T4.2_210	The DT simulation must simulate the network traffic and components based on built traffic patterns	The Digital Twin (DT) acts as an emulation environment for testing system behavior before real-world deployment. To accurately predict potential failures and cybersecurity threats, it must simulate realistic network traffic and system interactions based on historical traffic patterns and expected behaviors. Therefore, the DT can identify potential network bottlenecks, traffic anomalies, or untested scenarios that could cause operational issues.	DT	WINGS	UC3	It maps to the Digital Twin functional block
RIG_IMP_T4.2_230	The DASC must maintain detailed logs of all reconfiguration actions, including timestamps, affected components, and reasons for reconfiguration,	Given that DASC automates system adaptations, maintaining a comprehensive log of all reconfiguration events is essential for troubleshooting, auditing, and forensic analysis. These logs will allow administrators to track system changes, identify patterns of recurring interoperability issues, and investigate	DASC	WINGS	UC3	It maps to the Dynamic Service composition (DASC) functional component

	to support troubleshooting and auditing	potential security breaches caused by improper system reconfigurations.				
RIG_IMP_T4.3_320	The CPC should allow administrators to customize detection rules, thresholds, and response actions based on evolving cyber-physical threats.	The is a key component in real-time threat detection. However, cyber-physical threats are constantly evolving, requiring adaptive security measures. By allowing customization of detection rules, response thresholds, and automated countermeasures, administrators can tailor security policies to respond to specific threats targeting their infrastructure. This flexibility ensures that the CPC remains effective against emerging attack patterns.	CPC	WINGS	UC3	It maps to the Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC) functional component

4 UPDATED USE CASES DEFINITION

This section presents an updated version of the use cases definition, delving into the realistic attack scenarios and mitigations actions that can be detected and enforced through Rigorous. It should be noticed that use case UC2 IoT-Based Smart City Platform, defined originally in D2.1 by ICT-FI, was merged with UC4.

The Merge proposal for Use Cases 2 and 4 in the RIGOUROUS framework presents synergies and optimization opportunities. In this context, the convergence of the IoT-Based Smart City Platform (Use Case 2) and the PPDR (Public Protection and Disaster Relief) IoT Situational Awareness (Use Case 4) is crucial. The merging of these two use cases has a shared backend system architecture consisting of Microservices deployed on cloud resources. Despite differences in the information processed or generated by these microservices, they exhibit remarkable similarities in their foundational deployment and lifecycle management logic. This presents a chance for streamlined development and resource utilization, a key advantage of merging these two use cases. It is important to note that any changes made in allocated cloud resources should be carefully assessed to mitigate the risk of economic denial of sustainability. The autonomous lifecycle management of these microservices, empowered by resilient AI algorithms resistant to adversarial attacks, becomes a pivotal aspect of the merged Use Cases 2 and 4. Both use cases entail the integration of end-devices authenticating with the backend system and securely exchanging data while safeguarding the privacy of certain information. Applying homomorphic algorithms proves essential, especially for end-devices with limited capabilities. Encryption and decryption services can be provided, and the project's EaaS (Encryption as a Service) platform is a valuable resource.

The convergence enhances the efficiency of the individual use cases and aligns with a broader objective in the RIGOUROUS framework. Joint cooperation on authentication, data exchange, and privacy preservation can pave the way for collaborative initiatives. The outcomes of this collaboration can be documented and further developed into a publication, contributing valuable insights to an open-source software initiative for RIGOUROUS, fostering innovation and knowledge-sharing within the community. By considering these additional aspects, the merged use cases become holistic and contribute to the overarching goals of RIGOUROUS.

4.1. UC1

Use-Case 1 “Protection of 6G Infrastructures against Threats” has been described in D2.2 - “RIGOUROUS Use-Cases”, Section 3 (reference to D2.2 - Section 3). Following the receiving of valuable feedback, during our Interim Review, ORO, as Use-Case Owners are re-iterating on the “Authentication Abuse” threat condition in Threat Scenario 1, as described in D2.2, Section 3.2.1. Furthermore, a table mapping all threat conditions present in each threat scenario of Use-Case 1, and relevant and realistic mitigation actions, is provided below.

The iterative work for the updates reported in this deliverable has considered both the feedback received during the Interim Review, and the updates in the overall architecture, and implementations and integration of the RIGOUROUS components to ORO’s Testbed.

Updated Threat Scenario Description

The threat scenario assumes that the access to ORO's 6G Facility is monitored and protected through State-Of-The-Art deployments of security measures and operational best-practices.

4.1.1. Threat scenario 3.2.1.1.1 By Privilege Abuse:

A third-party sub-contractor, with administrative access to the 6G Facility, working in ORO's operational teams with roles in supervision of the 6G B2B services delivery processes, and infrastructures, has access to the Network Core components of the facility and the opportunity to abuse their administrative privileges, to modify the configuration of the Descriptors associated with specific services compositions for 6G B2B Services.

Motivated by disgruntlement to their contractual obligations, and by personal discontent for a specific customer of ORO's 6G B2B services, they will initiate the modification several services configurations, including slice allocation and slice configuration for this customer.

By accessing the CI/CD pipelines in use in the 6G Facility for the DevSecOps processes, this third-party operator will push a change to the Slicing component of the Core Network, to effectively reduce the QoS for a customer's slice to a low value of less than 1 Mbps. This will, in turn, adversely affect data and voice services availability for this customer.

The rationale for this scenario comes from industry-relevant events, which had happened in the close past, such as the attack on Vodafone's Portugal Network, affecting voice and data services across their national coverage[17].

This scenario is relevant to a number of practical deployments, such as is the case for Private Mobile Networks, and Cloud-Based Services hosted by Mobile Networks Operators.

Figure 1 - Diagram of UC1 - Scenario 1

Table 1 Relevant RIGOUROUS Mitigation Actions, per UC1 scenario

Scenario	Description of Threat (Attack)	Realistic Mitigation Actions
3.2.1.1.1	Unauthorized Access through Privilege Abuse by a third party, followed by malicious reconfiguration of 6G Services	SAE and DM Components monitor audit actions logged by the jump server used by this insider, to access the ORO's testbed admin interfaces. The AID, ISM and TRA components will assess the actions of the human-in-the-loop operator of effectively disrupting the SLAs and QoS for a given slice, and inform the SO and the Reaction Plane components, specifically the RM. The SO, in turn, will command an actuation, through the SM component, which will effectively revert the malicious reconfiguration of the customers' slice to the initial, good-known state.
3.2.1.1.2	Supply-chain attacks through the exploitation of erroneous configurations, and software vulnerabilities	
3.2.2.1	Information Gathering about Services and Devices in the 6G Facility	In this scenario, the SAE components, including the A.I. anomaly detection engine, the Cyber Physical Correlator, will detect the probing attempts of a malicious actor who is "scanning" the internet-facing perimeter of ORO's 6G Facility. The Cognitive Decision, Orchestration and Security Management Plane, will utilize AID and TRA capabilities to evaluate the risk, and through cooperation in the Reaction Plane components, instruct de SO to effectively orchestrate a change in the IPS/Firewall SoTA Cyber Security Plane of ORO's 6G Facility to include the offending IPs in deny lists.
3.2.3.1	Abnormal Traffic Scenario - Distributed Denial of Service Attacks targeting system components	In the case of the Abnormal traffic load (DDoS) scenario, RIGOUROUS should have the ability to detect the ongoing attack and trigger a change, within the 5G Orchestrators in the ORO 5G Facility, to isolate the malicious traffic to a dedicated slice, with a very low QoS value, effectively mitigating the attack. This threat scenario has been demonstrated in several instances, in RIGOUROUS, including during a PoC for EuCNC 2024. Further work is committed to demonstrate an end-to-end DDoS attack mitigation scenario across multiple domains, including ORO, UWS and UM testbeds.

4.2. UC3

Use-Case 3 “Utilities management and security” has been described in D2.2 - “RIGOUROUS Use-Cases”, Section 5 (reference to D2.2 - Section 5).

WINGS updated the use case, so as to extract a number of test cases scenarios, so as to facilitate our progress towards development and adaptation of assets and their subsequent integration.

4.2.1. RES sub-use case

Renewable energy production in Greece over 2024 reached 19,060 GWh, a significant jump from the 15,973 GWh of same period in 2023. Despite a promising shift toward green energy, grid constraints led to curtailments of 673 GWh of renewable energy—3.4% of RES production—in the first three quarters of 2024. April alone saw 259 GWh curtailed, nearly matching the total for all of 2023 (228 GWh). Greece could further reduce reliance on fossil fuels or imports, by minimizing curtailments in green energy production and potentially leading towards lower electricity prices [16].

The RES_CUT application is activated by dispatchers in Greece when there is an excess of RES beyond what can be absorbed by consumers.

The key entities/parameters of this real use case include:

- RES_CUT APPLICATION/CONTROLLER: System activated by dispatchers in Greece when there is an excess of renewable energy production (RES) beyond what can be absorbed by consumers.
- SETPOINT_BINOUT: The generation boundary that the application sent to the resource for reduction. The dispatchers set a limit in RES production and the RES_CUT application/controller sends SETPOINT_BINOUT every 8 sec.
- RES:Renewable Energy Source (photovoltaic panels or wind turbines)
- WINDC_ON = 0: if zero could not receive BINOUT command
- WINCSUSP = 1: if one means that the RES is in suspended mode and could not receive reduction signals. Note that sometimes there are cases in which the resource is set as suspended on purpose to have a reason not to follow the requested reduction.

Figure 2 - RES scenario topology

4.2.2. Security Threat Scenarios

As utility networks continue to evolve with cloud and mobile technologies, they become increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats. Ensuring the security of data, infrastructure, and communications is critical to maintaining reliable and resilient operations. The following sections outline key security threat scenarios that can impact the security framework of RIGOUROUS and how it mitigates these risks.

4.2.2.1. Data Security - Unauthorized access

The energy and utilities sector deals with a large amount of sensitive data, such as customer information and confidential business data. Hence, it's essential that this data is protected from unauthorized access and is only accessible to authorized personnel as data breaches are a serious concern for organizations in this sector and can have a major impact on their business.

Threat Scenario Description

One of the main challenges in securing utility networks is the presence of multiple domains that introduce several entry points for unauthorized access. Domains can range from diverse applications and systems within the utilities sector to different subsystems within a single system—such as IoT devices, gateways, edge computing, cloud infrastructure, and network components. When an attacker gains access to one of these domains, they can escalate privileges to extend their reach. Horizontal privilege escalation allows them to move laterally across interconnected systems, while vertical escalation enables them to gain higher control within a specific domain.

In this test scenario, unauthorized users attempt to infiltrate the RES control systems. The attacks can occur either on the source/equipment (RES_CUT APPLICATION/CONTROLLER, Gateway, RES) of the chain or the network that enables communication between the components.

Figure 3 - Test scenario 1: Unauthorised access

Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

The Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC) detects abnormal network behaviour through network traffic analysis and traffic flow and triggers security mechanisms in real-time. CPC transmits threats to AI-driven decision making (AID) via AID-CPC interface. AID sends mitigation measures to AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments (SO). SO deploys a firewall through a security policy to drop the packets originated from an attacker/intruder on the affected source/equipment (RES_CUT APPLICATION/CONTROLLER, Gateway, RES) of the chain or the network that enables communication between the components.

4.2.2.2. Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks

Attackers build botnets, large fleets of compromised devices, and use them to direct false traffic at your network or servers. DDoS can occur at the network level, for example by sending huge volumes of packets which can overwhelm a network or a server, or at the application level, for example by performing complex queries that bring a database to its limits.

Threat Scenario Description

DDoS attacks are a significant threat to modern network infrastructures. Malicious users or intruders build botnets to flood a target network or server with false traffic, rendering it inaccessible to legitimate users. These attacks can occur at different levels, either on network-level with high volumes of packet, leading to congestion and disruption, or application-level DDoS attacks targeting specific services by performing complex queries, exhausting system resources such as databases and web servers.

Given the interconnected nature of utility networks, such attacks can disrupt critical operations, preventing real-time monitoring and decision-making. Addressing these threats requires a combination of proactive monitoring, intelligent traffic filtering, and automated response mechanisms.

This test scenario deals with DDoS on equipment level. The attacks occur on the RES_CUT application/controller or the gateway.

Figure 4 - DDoS attacks to the RES controller or gateway

Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

Same as in Section 4.3.2.1.2. CPC monitors network traffic and detects patterns that suggest a DDoS attack is underway. The AI-driven decision-making system prioritizes mitigation measures, ensuring malicious traffic is blocked by the AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments (SO) before it can cause disruption. Therefore, the mitigation approach is traffic filtering and rate learning to drop excessive or suspicious requests before they overwhelm the network.

4.2.2.3. Code and data injection attacks

Several applications may be attacked to accept malicious user inputs and fail to validate and sanitize those inputs. Attackers can then fill out a form or make an API call, passing malicious code or data instead of the expected data values. The code is executed on the server and allows attackers to compromise it.

Threat Scenario Description

Code and data injection attacks occur when attackers manipulate input data or inject malicious code into a system to alter its behavior. The complexity of these attacks increases due to the presence of multiple domains, which multiply the entry points for injection attempts. Domains can include diverse applications and systems in utilities or different subsystems within the same system—such as IoT devices, gateways, edge computing, cloud infrastructure, and network components.

By targeting one of these domains, particularly IoT devices or gateways, attackers can escalate their actions, propagating erroneous data to additional, adjacent systems or gaining higher privileges within the same system. For example, a successful injection attack at the IoT or gateway level could allow malicious code or false data to flow upward to edge computing and cloud environments, disrupting decision-making and automation processes.

In this scenario, code and data injection attackers target the sequence of commands and information sent by the RES or the RES_CUT APPLICATION/CONTROLLER. Altering the SETPOINT_BINOUT values, the energy production, and the WINDC_ON, WINCSUSP variables, can lead to faulty decisions regarding the curtailment process. Also, the attacks can configure the (binary) parameters set by the RES itself as shown in the following figure. Malicious users attempt to manipulate RES control signals by injecting false data into the system.

Figure 5 - Code and data injection attack representation

Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

The Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC) detects anomalies in the data stream and triggers alerts, ensuring real-time protection against malicious actions. The AI-driven decision-making system prioritizes mitigation measures, ensuring malicious traffic is blocked by the AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments (SO) before it can cause disruption. Given the critical nature of energy systems, mitigating such attacks is essential to prevent incorrect command execution and system compromise.

4.2.2.4. Interoperability mismatches

One of the key challenges facing organizations in the utilities sector is that many legacy systems were not designed with interoperability and security in mind. Legacy systems often use proprietary protocols and standards that are not compatible with modern security tools and technologies. This makes it difficult to implement or deploy effective security controls/solutions in a mobile network and cloud environment.

Threat Scenario Description

Interoperability mismatches arise when systems, applications, or security tools are unable to communicate effectively. The complexity of this issue is amplified by the presence of multiple domains, each multiplying the number of systems that may fail to interoperate. These domains can include diverse applications and systems in the utilities sector or different subsystems within the same application or systems (IoT devices, gateways, edge computing, cloud infrastructure, and network components).

Any failure in the compatibility and interoperability among these systems, their domains, and security tools can lead to significant operational disruptions. These failures may prevent seamless data exchange, delay threat detection, and introduce vulnerabilities that attackers could exploit.

The consequences of interoperability mismatches range from inefficiencies in automated workflows to security gaps that compromise the resilience of the entire infrastructure.

For instance:

1. Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities require adapters or converters, which can introduce security loopholes.
2. Incompatible data formats can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data.
3. Organizations may struggle to enforce uniform security policies across diverse systems, leading to misconfigurations.

In the fourth test case scenario, we consider that it follows one of the previous 3 scenarios, in which the SO deploys a firewall through a security policy to drop the packets originated from an attacker/intruder Gateway. As a result, the traffic is rerouted and a new gateway is assigned to the RES, but this gateway uses a different protocol. Recommendations generated for interoperability issues between the different components are issued and applied, so that they can be fixed before security gaps are created.

Figure 6 - Interoperability mismatches representation

Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

Here, we need dynamic and automated service composition mechanisms, to detect and resolve the interconnection problems among components that are attempting to interoperate, and which are not known in advance. The Digital Twin (DT) runs a simulation to check the interoperability which detects the specific threat. Then, the DT triggers the DASC to detect and repair protocol mismatches between gateway and RES_CUT APPLICATION/CONTROLLER, preventing security vulnerabilities.

Table 2 Relevant RIGOUROUS Mitigation Actions, per UC3 scenario

Scenario	Description of Threat (Attack)	Realistic Mitigation Actions
4.3.2.1	Unauthorized users attempting to infiltrate the RES control systems to manipulate power distribution, targeting the RES_CUT application/controller, gateway, or RES.	The Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC) detects abnormal network behavior and triggers real-time security mechanisms. AI-driven decision-making (AID) collaborates with

		Security Orchestration (SO) to deploy firewall policies.
4.3.2.2.	Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks targeting the RES_CUT application/controller or gateway, causing network congestion and service disruption	CPC monitors network traffic and identifies patterns indicative of DDoS. AI-driven decision-making prioritizes mitigation measures, while SO enforces traffic filtering and rate limiting to drop excessive or suspicious requests before overwhelming the system.
4.3.2.3	Code and Data Injection attacks targeting control signals between the RES, RES_CUT application/controller, and gateway, leading to false decisions in the curtailment process.	CPC analyzes network traffic for anomalies and raises alerts. AI-based Security Orchestration (SO) blocks malicious traffic.
4.3.2.4	Protocol mismatches between IoT devices, gateways, cloud/6G infrastructure that can lead to security threats, such as: a) Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities that require adapters or converters, which can introduce security loopholes, b) Incompatible data formats that can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data, c) Misconfigurations, due to non-ability to enforce uniform security policies across diverse systems.	The Digital Twin (DT) runs a simulation to check the interoperability which detects the specific threat. Dynamic Automated Service Composition (DASC) detects and resolves interconnection issues by reconfiguring components and adapting interfaces.

4.3. UC4

UC4 “PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform” has been previously described in D2.2 - “RIGOUROUS Use-Cases”, Section 6 [Reference]. Considering the feedback received during and after RV1, the threat mitigation conditions associated with the threat scenarios have been reviewed. For simplicity purposes, both the threat scenario description and respective mitigation approaches and relevant tools are replicated (with respective adjustments) below.

4.3.1. PPDR scene and teams provisioning

4.3.1.1. Threat Scenario Description

Whenever a new operation begins, and throughout its course, many different teams and elements will arrive and join the operation, from field operatives to on-premises control operations. This means multiple devices being connected to the infrastructure that need secure authentication and authorization to access not only the services but also the network itself. As such, one possible threat is for unwanted devices to try to authenticate against the network and get access to the services

deployed, which would have implications in terms of privacy as well as security and trust. Moreover, it could also be the case where in some situations, there would be a need for teams the use personal devices, usually referred to as Bring Your Own Device (BYOD). This increases the need for security analysis, since at the start, these devices are deemed insecure until an analysis is made. Because PPDR events are usually isolated and occur occasionally, the Mobitrust platform might be deployed on demand, whenever it is needed at a given location. For this, a cloud/infrastructure manager will trigger the deployment of the platform, letting the orchestrator take control and manage it.

4.3.1.2. Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

The secure deployment of the Mobitrust platform via the Onboarding Tools, together with the network isolation on all communications, from the end-devices to the cloud, through slicing (enabled by the Slice Manager), will allow decreasing the chances of any device intrusion, going from the device registration in the network and slice access to continuous monitoring of the deployed services leveraging the continual and federated based anomaly detection frameworks (R12 RIGOUROUS Assets). The *Multi-Domain AI-driven Orchestrator* will be one of the key components in the full cycle orchestration, taking control from the initial deployment of the application, throughout the course of the operation, and ending with a controlled wrap-up of the scenario, taking any necessary actions for removing the deployment when it is no longer needed.

During the life-cycle of the provisioning operations, in case of rogue devices being detected or failures in the bootstrapping of certain devices, alerts will be generated by the RIGOUROUS assets, being analysed by a cloud analyst and/or a platform analyst, but also processed automatically by the RIGOUROUS SOAR and acted upon following the Zero Touch Paradigm. Such kind of failures may be detected through the anomaly detection frameworks, reported to the AI-Driven decision engine, which will determine the best policy to apply and communicate it to the Security Orchestrator. Then, this will interact with the most appropriate policy enforcer and ensure the proper enforcement, ultimately leading to the threat mitigation.

4.3.2. Intrusion into system to access privileged information or cause disruption of services

4.3.2.1. Threat Scenario Description

While the systems are deployed, an intrusion may be detected in the network, coming from anywhere in the infrastructure. This intrusion may have multiple purposes, from eavesdropping and trying to acquire sensitive information about ongoing/past operations, to causing harm, by making changes to the data and/or manipulating actions under execution.

4.3.2.2. Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

In order to improve the security of the deployed services and minimize/stop any attack being made, continuous monitoring will be a key feature, using AI-based mechanisms for the detection and mitigation of the ongoing attacks. Anomaly detection, namely through the use of unsupervised ML techniques part of the RIGOUROUS R12 Assets, may have a key impact on improving the detection of unknown attacks, allowing to take any needed measures. Moreover, defence mechanisms, such as, MTD, can also take a key role in increasing the security of the deployed services.

The detection of such intrusions or anomalies by the RIGOUROUS functional components will trigger its SOAR to act accordingly (somehow similar to the process previously described), while the alerts coming from those assets can also be inspected by the infrastructure analysts, which may decide to later on take different measures or not. This post-incident analysis can also loop back into the AI-driven decision mechanisms to further enhance the analysis and decision-making processes, contributing to more suitable and accurate AI/ML approaches.

4.3.3. Disclosure of device vulnerability or unlawful appropriation of a device

4.3.3.1. Threat Scenario Description

Throughout the course of an ongoing operation, it could be disclosed that one or more equipment have disclosed vulnerabilities identified. Moreover, it could also happen that a device is lost or stolen amidst the stress of the operation. As such, appropriate measures must be taken to address both these scenarios.

4.3.3.2. Mitigation Approach and Relevant Tools

Since the devices used in these scenarios have access to restricted networks and information, having any sort of vulnerability detected or unlawful usage poses high security threats. As such, dealing with these cases is of paramount importance. Whenever either of these cases occurs, the steps to take is to erase all information from the devices (using remote control channels implemented in the devices), followed by the necessary steps to unauthorize the device in the network and in the platform itself, so that it can no longer connect to any of the secure channels nor to the Mobitrust platform.

Similarly to the above scenarios, the detection of such cases should be swiftly acted upon by the RIGOUROUS SOAR, while also generating the necessary alerts which will allow the analysts to do a proper inspection of the issues and take extra/different measures if deemed necessary.

The following table presents the relevant RIGOUROUS Mitigation Actions for the UC4 scenarios:

Table 3 UC4 Mitigation Actions

Scenario	Description of Threat (Attack)	Realistic Mitigation Actions
4.4.1	Multiple devices attempting to connect and authenticate into the network in a PPDR event, potentially with personal devices (BYOD paradigm). Need for local and on-demand deployment of the Mobitrust platform.	Secure deployment via Onboarding Tools for appropriate security and privacy concerns handling. Network mechanisms like network slicing (provided by the RIGOUROUS Slice Manager) can provide a dedicated channel for the multiple devices to connect and establish the data plane, aiming to share multiple IoT data and

		video streams with the Mobitrust CCC.
4.4.2	Network intrusion	Continuous network traffic monitoring and analysis using RIGOUROUS R12's Assets, providing real-time traffic anomaly detection. Moving target defense AI-based techniques can also applied. Detected anomalies will be handled by the RIGOUROUS SOAR.
4.4.3	Disclosed equipment vulnerabilities and/or rogue devices (lost or stolen).	Erase all the information from the devices in question. Unauthorize and unauthenticate the devices from the network and from the Mobitrust platform.

5 FINAL RIGOUROUS ARCHITECTURE

Deliverable D2.1 identified and explained the five main pillar in RIGOUROUS. The architecture is comprised of multiple Security Management Domains (SMD) that provide the security management services, as a specialized kind of management services considered in the ZSM ETSI architecture [1], for envisioned 6G networks. These security management functional blocks are grouped in planes (Design, Monitoring and Analytics, Cognitive Decision, Orchestration and Management, Reaction) to represent better the Security Orchestration Automation Response (SOAR [5]) closed loop approach.

It should be noted that the architecture is based on ZSM reference architecture, but it is not intended to fully comply with such a reference architecture.

The architecture is based on 5 main pillars enumerated below:

- Zero-touch network and Service Management (Automated and Closed Loop Operation)
- SOAR (Security, Orchestration, Automation, Response)
- DevSecOps
- ZeroTrust
- Artificial Intelligence as a Service

For further information about the main pillars the reader is referred to section 5 of deliverable D2.1

5.1. Global architecture

Figure 7: RIGOUROUS Final High-level Functional Architecture (HLFA)

Figure 3 shows the final version high level functional architecture of RIGOUROUS. The architecture dedicates different planes for handling the whole life cycle of smart services in 6G networks satisfying the security, privacy, and trust requirements.

The framework addresses the main stages of DevSecOps, encompassing the design/development of services and their security-privacy requirements, devices onboarding specification, automated provisioning and onboarding of security-privacy requirements, real-time operation reconfiguration, management, and maintenance.

The Framework supports multi-domain scenarios and in order to do that, the functional components have the dual implementation to cope End-to-end scenarios in multitenant and multi-domain scenarios. To this aim, the Rigorous architecture features a Cross-domain Integration Fabric that support interfaces to enable communication between Rigorous components placed in different domains.

Design phase

At the design stage, depicted in green on Figure 3, the architecture supports diverse security and privacy tools for net-app developers and networks/system administrators, including Human Controllable Privacy (PUI), and Intent Based security formal modelling (SMUI) tools aimed to define in a user-friendly manner their smart-services and associated security, trust and privacy models.

The interfaces and access methods below have been described in more detail in the scope of WP3.:

- Human Controllable Privacy (PUI)
- Intent Based security formal modelling (SMUI)
- Risk Management (RS)
- App Onboarding Specification (AOUI)
- Security Onboarding Specification (SOUI)

The main changes regarding the first version presented in D2.1 are the followings. The service composition box has been removed from the original architecture version, as the Dynamic and Automated service composition (DSC) is not, in the end, driven by user intents and design stage.

Besides, the Response and mitigation policies box has been also removed from the original version of the architecture as it collides with the “Intent-based security formal Modelling” (SMUI) functional box. In addition the risk management box is no longer an GUI, but rather specifications. It does not preclude that in future versions of the architecture beyond Rigorous this GUI could be implemented.

Operations phase

Operations Monitoring and analytics.

The Monitoring and analytics plane in Figure 3, is responsible for the misbehaviour detection that could happen in the network by considering different monitoring agents deployed either at vertical layers or horizontally in any network-segment. It explores both filtering activities and data analysis for detecting different anomalies relying on AI.

Across all network layers, the framework might have the capability to create an adaptive profile for devices, such as software vulnerabilities and misconfigurations. Existing Threat Intelligence from CTI feeds can be correlated to improve detection accuracy. The control layer monitoring capabilities should have in focus the SDN and Cloud Computing platforms and services. The Application Layer should benefit from enhanced monitoring and detection of threats related to VNFs, VMs and could achieve intelligence management capabilities using 6G-ZTS.

The monitoring feeds the AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine functional component. A special purpose Cyber Physical Correlators service of SAE might consider behavioural information, events, and network data from diverse sources, e.g., sensors and cameras, to perform a real-time anomaly detection of utilities-grid. It could perform the detection based on different schemes such as rules-based system, ML approach for intrusion patterns recognition and root cause analysis.

The Privacy-preserving AI-based anomaly detection service of SAE might consider the high demands imposed by multi-domain and multi-tenant beyond 5G networks as well as IoT devices to detect threats and attacks, while keeping privacy-preservation of the exchanged federated AI-models and Cyber-Threat Intelligence (CTI) data. Thus, SAE might integrate AI-based algorithms for anomaly-based detection of evolving attacks perpetrated either against network infrastructures or final hosts (including IoT devices), at either network-level or application-level. The anomaly-based analysis might support the ability to detect zero-days attacks carried out in 5G-IoT networks and multiple and heterogeneous computing platforms (edge/core/cloud) provided by different domains, segments, and technologies.

The architecture shall monitor in real-time the network traffic gathering telemetry data, processing, and aggregating packets in conversation flows in Data Services (DS), extracting additional meaningful network features as statistics that are dynamically analysed in SAE in streaming for a fully distributed AI-based anomaly detection. To this aim, the architecture should have the ability to distribute agents across network Edges and Fog Nodes and combine different AI techniques to increase accuracy in attack detection, thereby capturing normal behaviour patterns and detecting anomalies (zero-days).

Thus, AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE) component is trained continuously in a federated way and fed by the shared AI trained models exchanged through the Cyber Threat Information (CTI) functional component. The anomaly detection might be extended towards the edge of the network, which collaborate between each other for efficient and accurate detection. Thus, federated machine learning approaches on IoT and MEC systems have been investigated, with efficient management of the limited computation and communication resources, thereby achieving optimal learning performance. In SAE, Federated Learning algorithms might be combined with privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) through specialized services, to anonymize the exchanged data during the learning process, ensuring a fully privacy-respectful of exchanged AI models. Thus, SAE might take benefits of PETs in empowering privacy preservation but considering communication, computation and accuracy degradation issues that can emerge from integrating PETs.

To enhance anomaly detection, privacy-preserving Cyber Threat intelligent (CTI) sharing shall be embedded in the framework by design. The data to be exchanged includes not only Indicators of Compromise (IoC) modelled and exchanged through format such as Structured Threat Information eXpression (STIX) and platform such as MISP, but also other meaningful security information including software updates and packages, mitigation actions, and trained AI models aimed to detect cyberattacks. The CTI data sharing allows a full control of the data exchanged across organizations, with selective, privacy-preserving, fine-grained access control and minimal disclosure of personal-sensible information in the process of data exchange. In addition, privacy-enhanced technologies (PETs) shall be onboarded to anonymize sensible exchanged information.

The SAE functional component might provide novel Moving Target Defence services that define diverse strategies to further increase the resilience level of ML models and foster proactive defence against adversarial attacks. The envisioned MTD approaches shall rely on AI to determine the best MTD strategy, enabling constant and strategic update of the ML models incorporated in the deployed security control loop, by deciding how and when the model modifications (i.e., update) should be performed to make the ML model robust without sacrificing its performance and with reduced moving cost.

Cognitive Decision, Orchestration and Management

The architecture is endowed with a Zero-Trust Security and Identity Management component that shall be instantiated through different services for trust evaluation and enabler service functionalities (TESF) to perform continuous trust evaluation of entities or functions (i.e., including PNF and VNFs at the RAN and Core, application functions and end-user devices associated to the network), trust quantification and validation to ensure minimization of potential impacts, such as security breach, lateral threat movement and service failure.

The Trust evaluation and enabler service of the ZTM shall consider various factors such as monitoring data including behavioural or environmental attributes, monitoring the integrity or security posture of the involved function or entity in the communication system, potential service violations, malicious operations etc., to evaluate the trustworthiness and to estimate the service reliability and resilience of the target under trust evaluation (i.e., a function or entity which is under trust evaluation/being evaluated is referred as 'Target'). To this end, trust evaluation and enabler service might apply AI algorithms for trust related evaluation analytics and predictions. Based on the evaluated trust information, the TEF can provide notifications to the trust service consumers. Any network or application function which consumes or provides services, to and from the evaluation target, can subscribe to the trust service as consumers to get proactive notifications about the trustworthiness of the target. The trust service consumers might utilize the trust data notification to determine and allow/deny further service consumption or service provision, respectively, for the target. In case a target is evaluated to have less trust or is compromised, the trust service consumer can invoke potential network operation (e.g., reassignment of serving network functions for the end user or for the network service consumers as applicable) to ensure the service continuation (i.e., for the end-users and the network functions respectively). The trust data can also be utilized by the operator to configure network management functions to isolate and fix the security issues (e.g., vulnerabilities) of the evaluated target.

In case an anomaly is detected, the AI-driven Decision-making functional component evaluates the outcomes from prediction and detection reported by SAE and then shall make use of different ML models over the real-time contextual models and risk assessments from the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) to figure out the intents and response, performing whenever necessary data fusion with data coming from diverse layers and networks segments. Thus, the AI-driven decision-making component aims to initially prioritize the identified threats and devise a proposed mitigation plan whilst creating a threat orchestration plan. The framework prioritize threats and come up with a mitigation plan that feeds the threat orchestration ecosystem. Several Data Services providing meaningful data to the framework such as Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) services can be used as baseline.

Then, the decision module contacts the security orchestrator, which in turn, works out the physical and virtual function chaining, best enabler to enforce a particular policy to be enforced cross-level, cross-network segments, and cross-domains to enforce the intents. The orchestrator is driven by AI to make their chaining and orchestration decision and rely on special modules to translate the intents, policies and behavioural profiles coming from the decision into concrete actions. The orchestrator can be also invoked for re-configuring, during operation, the virtual network security functions and associated low-level intents and policies. To this aim, the security orchestrator shall consider among others, network parameters such as QoS capacities, capabilities, actual resources CPU, RAM, storage, system status, and current deployed policies. The orchestrator might interface with the Response and mitigation module of the reaction plane to enforce certain countermeasure cross-vertical layers, either at application-services layer, information layer or infrastructure.

The architecture might provide security keeper functional aspects through the Security Threat Risk Assessment in the architecture.

The deployment of the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) service begins with the Onboarding Tools component, which initializes the TRA using a configuration file. This configuration file defines key parameters such as Kafka broker settings, topic names for anomaly and risk score events, the CVE database source, and the system model location. By ensuring a structured deployment process, the onboarding tools allow the TRA to adapt to different testbed environments and configurations efficiently.

The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) service receives the Threat Identification and Threat Type information from the Anomaly Detection provided by the R12 assets and assesses the Level of Risk using an internal risk matrix and contextual mitigation factors provided by external services.

The TRA receives the Threat information from the Anomaly Detector R12 together with the vulnerability characteristics of the asset or resource targeted by the attack or potentially compromised during its execution. This last information is retrieved from the System Model corresponding to the use case scenario and its related testbed. The system model comprises the list of assets and their place within the system's network topology.

Note: "Asset" to be considered include:

- End user device, application or resource,
- IoT, machine to machine end points of communication channels,
- Cloud or network resources hosting customer assets.

The vulnerability information is retrieved from one of the management/data services instantiated by RIGOUROUS framework or alternatively may be retrieved from external vulnerability repositories such as:

- The NIST National Vulnerability Data Base (<https://nvd.nist.gov/general>) [2],
- The MITRE Common Vulnerability & Exposure ([HTTPS://WWW.CVE.ORG/](https://www.cve.org/)) [3],

Given the threat information and the vulnerability signature of the resource under attack, the Threat Risk Assessor establishes the potential impact (severity) of the Threat.

The Threat Risk Assessor processes the information and returns to the AID Risk Score using, for instance, a qualitative or semi-Quantitative risk scale (low {0-2}, Medium {3-5}, High {6-8}).

Reaction plane

The Reaction Plane oversees enforcing appropriate actions for adapting the system to the actual context, changing the components and their interconnections at runtime, and enforcing strategies for mitigation of the threats. Thus, the reaction plane oversees the services in run-time for dynamic reconfiguration, relying on Dynamic and Automated Service Composition functional component to ensure and automate the interconnection and the interoperability capabilities of service components in high dynamic scenarios. Such aspects are crucial for dynamic systems (e.g., IoT/Edge), which are expected to scale up and to face unknown situations and should be extensible to support new components without re-engineering those currently deployed. The DSC provides a monitoring and adaptation framework to detect interconnection/interoperability issues and to adapt components at run-time, especially when emphasis is on dynamics, to allow the system to continue to operate. Additionally, the Digital Twin functional component might provide a simulated

model of different components that interact with each other to help identify and propose actions on interconnection/interoperability issues for the Dynamic automated service composition.

Regarding the threat mitigation, the architecture has the ability to come up with mitigation strategies for countering cyberattacks in any network segment of the 6G network, either at the PNFs, VNFs, IoT devices, applications, or services by directly interacting with these components and/or the network interconnecting them. In this regard, the Response-Mitigation functional component has been endowed with novel actuators for recovery and response mechanism for mitigating attacks such as Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attack. To reap the benefits of network slicing in enabling profitable beyond 5G services, as RM function component takes advantage of the emerging ML techniques, to develop a reliable dynamic resource provisioning scheme for strategic auto-scaling of end-to-end network slices in multi-domain and multi-tenant setting that counteracts the performance degradation and sustainability loss impacts engendered by EDoS attacks while meeting the agreed SLA requirements of different services. Furthermore, as network actuator, part of the Response Mitigation component the architecture has the ability to enforce end-to-end multi-domain and multitenant network slicing mechanism as self-healing, that allows isolating attackers in dedicated slices, while keeping network SLAs to legitimate users.

Vertical layers

At infrastructure layer, diverse controllers and managers such as SDN controllers, Virtualization Orchestrators, IoT Controllers and Managers interconnect the PNFs, VNFs, IoT devices, services, and applications for enabling different cross-domain and cross-tenant IoT-Edge-Cloud smart-services continuum.

At this level in the infrastructure layer, RIGOUROUS might handle the B5G devices through the Bootstrapping and Onboarding management, preventing unauthorized access and privilege escalation. AI security orchestration is used to individually take the device capabilities and constraints into account to deliver the most applicable security level in the system on device granularity. Zero-touch credential bootstrapping with trusted and verifiable application onboarding ensures the smooth integration of new devices without human interaction and the integrity of the desired applications and services in the system.

5.2. Functional Components descriptions

The functional components identified in the architecture are barely same that the ones already defined in deliverable D2.1, the descriptions are included here again for the sake of completeness.

The functional blocks on the operation side are:

- **AI driven decision (AID):** The AI-Service, Threat Type Detection and Classification uses data from the AI Driven Cyber Physical Correlator functional block and Privacy-preserving Federated AI Anomaly Detection to identify cyber threats and intrusions. The AI-driven decision-making process includes data pre-processing, parallel classification, and AI/ML actual processing algorithms. The main technical objectives are to develop a hybrid AI functionality for threats and intrusion patterns recognition, providing root cause analysis. The goal is to develop a dedicated experimental design plan for heterogeneous networks involving multiple data streams and massive data input. The AI-driven decision making will prioritize threats and inform the AI-driven orchestrator for the right mitigation plan. The

main capabilities are threat and intrusion pattern recognition and root cause analysis. Taking as input the threat type, it provides scores and trust information to the Zero Trust Security Data, evaluations to the Threat Risk Assessor Data and threat risk levels to the AI security orchestrator.

- **Threat risk assessor (TRA):** The service receives threat information from the AID and assesses the level of risk using the internal risk matrix and contextual mitigation factors. It considers the vulnerability characteristics of the target or resource, such as end user devices, IoT, and cloud resources. The TRA determines the potential impact and trust posture of the information and returns a risk score to the AID using a qualitative or semi-quantitative risk scale. The main capability is the assessment of the risk score as a function of threat, vulnerability, trust level.
- **Zero trust and identity management (ZTM):** Zero Trust management is a security approach that focuses on minimizing access to network assets and resources, based on authentication, authorization, and security posture of the requestor. This approach proposes event-based data collection to identify security risks and threats. This allows operators to evaluate and monitor security results, enabling the creation of access control policies that enforce fine-grained access control to prevent threat lateral movement. The RIGOUROUS Framework offers a Zero Trust Management function that collects event information related to violations of normal behaviours, service requests, critical configuration changes, load, status, and resource utilization. This data is then provided to the Operator's security evaluation and monitoring function, which receives security monitoring results in the form of trust data. The main capability is related to the collection of Network Functions related data from the Network Repository Function (NRF).
- **AI driven security orchestrator (SO):** This functional block is responsible for enforcing security requirements through virtual network security functions (VSF) and the service enforces security policies for the local domain, deploying necessary security agents through Intent-Based Security Management, Slice Manager, or NFV MANO. It can also orchestrate policy enforcements on multiple domains to cover security configuration requirements. This allows SO to respond automatically to actual contexts and prevent future threats. It receives mitigation policies from the AI-driven Decision Engine. The SO communicates with other functional blocks, such as the ISM for conflict detection, NFV MANO for deployment, Zero Trust Identity Management for trust scores, and the Slice Manager for security end-to-end slices. The main capability is to enforce or remove security policies.
- **Intent based security management (ISM):** The functional block transforms abstract Protection Level and Security Level requirements into specific parameters for AI-driven Security Orchestrators. It provides a framework for defining Security Service Level Agreements, refines them into deployment-ready representations, enforces them in real time, and prevents conflict detection.

The functional blocks on the monitoring and analytics side are:

- **AI driven security analytics engine (SAE):** The block provides insights and predictions of a domain's security conditions based on data collected from managed entities within the domain. It offers services such as the Anomaly Detection service, Federated Training service, Privacy-Enhancing service, MTD service, and Cyber Physical Correlator service. The Anomaly

Detection service detects abnormal behaviour resulting from malicious or unintentional actions by identifying patterns in data. The Federated Training service allows knowledge sharing between SAEs of different domains without exchanging local data. The Privacy-Enhancing service uses various PETs to promote privacy-preservation. The MTD service protects the ML models against adversarial attacks. The Cyber Physical Correlator service uses Machine Learning algorithms to detect and mitigate anomalies and cyber-threats. The main capability is to notify the anomalies to the service consumer, the AI-driven decision engine and the data services.

- **Privacy preserving CTI sharing (CTI):** This functional block enables Cyber Threat Information exchange between domains, offering privacy-enhancing techniques (PETs) to protect sensitive data. The asset consists of a privacy-preserving service that obfuscates sensitive attributes based on user-specified policies, and a Threat Intelligence Platform (TIP) that publishes events from the service or assets. Examples of CTI information generated from the RIGOUROUS platform include attacks, decisions, AI models, security requirements, telemetry and flow statistics data, and software updates. The main capability is malware event publication.
- **Data services (DS):** This module allows the different functions to persist data that can be shared by functions in one or more domains.
- **Data monitoring (DM):** The aim of the block is to monitor data from the managed infrastructure, and it covers the Topology Service, which discovers devices and network ports available in the managed infrastructure. The southbound interface performs partial discovery of the existing topology, without defining a reference point. The northbound interface provides an updated list of discovered hosts, devices, and network ports. It provides information on the reported devices and network ports discovered in the managed infrastructure to the Slice Mitigation Planning Service.

The functional blocks on the monitoring and analytics side are:

- **Digital Twin (DT):** A service that inputs a system model with annotations for interoperability, security, privacy, and trust requirements, providing insights for Dynamic automated service composition to identify mismatches and propose solutions.
- **Dynamic and automatic service composition (DSC):** The block detects and resolves interconnection issues among components, addressing protocol mismatches, encoding mismatches, notation mismatches, and units. It suggests conversions, source code changes, container changes, ontology identification, and machine learning algorithms for problem classification. It has the capability to categorize the causes that cause the mismatches.
- **Response mitigation (RM):** The block aims to enforce mitigation strategies for cyber-attacks. It provides two services: the Slice Control Service, which enforces quality of service requirements for network slicing, and the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator Service, which uses Deep Learning to discriminate malicious resource scaling requests from legitimate load. It has the capabilities to create or delete network slices, associate or de-associate a network flows to a network slice.

5.3. General Flows

Proactive Flow

Figure 8: Proactive Flow in the Final High-level architecture

The proactive flow refers to the interaction between blocks as shown in Figure 4. It should be noticed that most of the content of this proactive flow was already defined in D2.1 and has been added here again for the sake of completeness.

(1) The initial Intent, Security Policy or Security Service Level Agreement (SSLA) is defined by the operator or domain administrator using the SMUI specifications or onboarding tools and it is sent to the Intent-Based Security Management (ISM) module. An external entity, such as an over-the-top streaming, could also invoke the ISM directly without the SMUI tool to request security services to the operator. The Security Orchestrator could also receive directly the SSLAs and then contact the ISM for policy management including translation and conflict detection.

The data format and language used for the communication with the ISM, is expected to be based on an abstract high-level language for User-centric model representation. The ISM checks possible conflicts between the policy(es) to be enforced and policies already enforced by the ISM.

Alternatively, the proactive flow, also consider interactions from other Onboarding tools that can consider risk scores to enforce security and privacy policies

(2) The ISM module communicates the requested Security Policy to the Security Orchestrator for enforcement.

- (3) The Security Orchestrator relies on ISM services to refine the User Centric Security Policy, and the ISM provides medium-level secure policy description using MSPL language.
- (4) The Security orchestrator accesses to the Data Services component (DS) in particular a System model that keeps track of the network topologies and infrastructure. It allows to obtain information about available MANOS, slice managers or allocation managers. It also accesses DS to get the specific enabler/asset that must be enforced, topology/infrastructure information.
- (5) The Security Orchestrator might communicate with the with the Zero Trust Manager (ZTM) to get indexes and scores about the services, infrastructure and/or resources involved in the SLA or policy, that allows prioritizing deployment solutions that are enforced or going to be enforced.
- (6) When the intent or policy is an End-to-End (E2E) policy, i.e., involves one or more different domains, the E2E Security Orchestrator service of the (OS) functional block contacts other domain-level Security Orchestrator services of other SMD to let them enforce the domain-level security policies in the corresponding domain.
- (7) Each security orchestrator in each involved domain receives its corresponding domain-level policy that is first checked for potential conflicts and/or impossibility of fulfilment by the ISM module before being transmitted back the Domain-level Security Orchestrator for enforcement.
- (8) Each Security Orchestrator in its domain relies on its ISM service to translate the domain-level policy into specific low-level actions that can be enforced on the domain infrastructure.
- (9) At each domain, the domain-level Security Orchestrator communicates with its domain-level Zero Trust Manager (ZTM) to get indexes and scores about the services, infrastructure and/or resources involved in the SLA or policy, that allows prioritizing deployment solutions that are enforced or going to be enforced.
- (10) The security policies can be enforced on any segment of the network domain. Depending on the situation, it can be enforced either directly on the resources in (e.g., configuration of new rules on a deployed vFirewall (Virtual Firewall) at the Core or Cloud) or via the Unified Security API offered by the network/service orchestration through MANO services (e.g., instantiation of new security VNFs and their chaining), or contacting specific IoT Controllers, SDN Controllers, Slice Managers, Security Agents. The Federated Learning agents can be deployed also as virtual network functions by the orchestrator using FL-policies, to perform the AI training.

Reactive flow

Figure 9: Reactive Flow in the High-level architecture

This section describes the general flow aimed to achieve a smart closed loop for reactive/adaptive security protection in B5G networks comprised of multiple domains. Most of the content here was already defined in D2.1, included here for the sake of completeness.

- (1) Once the security policies are enforced in the network/system during the design/proactive phase, the data on the network performance and security are collected through Security Agents towards the Data Monitoring (DM) component in each security management domain.
- (2) The information gathered from monitoring is stored by Data Services (DS), this information could be topology information, data-path/control-path network information, system information, service(s) assets, enablers available, etc. The most important data service is the System Model service that keeps network topology and infrastructure information. Another kind of Data services can be a Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) platform.
- (3) Information about Cyber Threat Information, such as Indicators of Compromise (IoC) in data formats such as MISP or Structured Threat Information eXpression (STIX), can be also received and shared through the CTI component, and stored in DS for later processing by the Security Analytics engine. To this aim, specific services can take care of privacy preservation issues in CTI sharing.
- (4) The security Analytics Engine (SAE) can detect any potential violation of the policies enforced and can perform real-time network and security anomaly detection. It can be done by different Services such as Privacy-preserving FL anomaly detectors. The workflow for Federated learning deployment and training should have been done previously. In parallel, AI-driven Cyber Physical

Correlator and other similar services such as (conversation/metrics processors) services belonging to the SAE can aggregate-process incoming events from the Data Monitoring and DS services that can be further processed by other Analytics SAE services.

(5) If an anomaly/incident is detected by SAE, it informs the Domain's Decision Engine. AI-driven Decision-making mitigation framework module evaluates the outcomes from prediction and detection reported by SAE and initially prioritize the identified threats and devise a proposed mitigation plan. There can be dedicated services to make specialized decisions, for instance slice Decision services to determine concrete parameters associated to network slicing mitigation decisions.

(6) The Decision component (AID) can gather Trust information from ZTM components at each Security Management Domain to get E2E trustiness score calculations and make decisions accordingly. In this regard, the ZTM performs continuous trust evaluation of entities or functions (i.e., including PNF and VNFs at the RAN and Core, application functions and end-user devices associated to the network), trust quantification and validation to ensure minimization of potential impacts, such as security breach, lateral threat movement and service failure.

(7) The Decision component can also gather information from the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) to make mitigation plans accordingly. The TRA component interfaces with the CTI component and system model to the vulnerabilities and infrastructure information need to compute the risk scores.

(8) To make sophisticated mitigation plans the AID decision can contact the Response-Mitigation (RM) component.

(9) The Dynamic and Automated Service Composition (DSC) might gather information from Digital Twins (DT) component to compute the repair actions as mitigation plan to enforce, considering the actual context from Data Services and previous experiments and simulations from DT component.

(10) The Response-Mitigation (RM) component might gather information from the Dynamic and Automated Service Composition (DSC) that detects potential protocol mismatches or misconfigurations that can lead to network failures and security issues. If the DSC detects protocol mismatches or misconfigurations, DSC investigates the appropriate repair actions, so as to resolve the protocol mismatches or misconfigurations. The Dynamic and Automated Service Composition (DSC) sends the repair actions as mitigation plan to the Response-Mitigation (RM) to enforce the mitigation. The workflow continues in step (15).

(11) Once the Decision (AID) component has computed the mitigation plan (relying on the RM in step 8), the AID informs the security orchestration about the decision plan to enforce (using MSPL policy language).

(12) The Security Orchestrator can check conflicts in the plan by contacting the ISM. To do so, the ISM might consider policies already deployed and actual context gathered from data-services.

(13) If the mitigation plan involves different domains, the E2E orchestrator service contacts other Security Orchestrators placed in other domains to enforce the corresponding domain-level mitigation plan.

(14) The Security Orchestrator (SO) contacts the Response-Mitigation (RM) to enforce the mitigation. The RM makes use of novel actuators that are implemented as a service. These services can include recovery and response mechanisms for mitigating attacks, such as for instance the Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attack mitigator service, or the Slice control Service, (a self-healing mechanism that allows isolating attackers in dedicated slices, while keeping network SLAs to legitimate users).

(15) The chosen Response-Mitigation Service of the RM component applies the mitigation action on the system by contacting its associated security agents and managers.

(16) In addition, or simultaneously with step 14 the SO can also enforce directly security policies as reaction policies contacting directly MANO, Manager and Security Agents (in a similar way as described in the last step of the proactive flow).

5.4. Detailed processes flows in the architecture

The following subsections describe the main process flows that have been identified in the architecture to fulfil the project goals. The workflows refers to the interactions between the functional components of the architecture. Each workflow includes the main services that have been designed and are being implemented for each functional component, along with the main interfaces of those services. It should be noticed that this is not a exhaustive interfaces and service definition, as those implementation details are defined in deep in WP5.

The workflows definitions have been splitted in each of the main task developed in the technical workpackages, i.e. WP3 and WP4.

- Onboarding, devsecops and devpriops (T3.1)
- Security orchestration and enforcement (T3.2)
- Zero trust (T3.3)
- 6g network slicing (T3.4)
- AI-based anomaly detection (T4.1)
- Automated service composition and digital twin (T4.2)
- AI-based decision (T4.3)
- Risk assessment (T4.3)
- Response and mitigation (T4.4)

5.4.1. Onboarding, DevSecOps and DevPriOps

The onboarding process follows DevSecOps and DevPrivOps principles, continuously assessing service risk and privacy preservation throughout the lifecycle of network services. Services are onboarded using the Onboarding Tools (OT), which also document their security and privacy capabilities within their specifications.

Once a service is onboarded, the OT requests the Privacy Quantifier to generate a privacy report, which includes a privacy score and relevant tags indicating the confidentiality of the data handled by the service. This score is incorporated into the service specification, and the service is categorized in the RIGOUROUS service catalog based on its assigned tags.

Next, the OT requests a risk assessment from the TRA, which calculates and embeds the risk score within the service. This information, along with user-defined policies, are then forwarded to the Security Orchestrator, which manages the deployment by sending policies to a designated enabler, the NMTD. The NMTD subsequently instantiates the service in the selected infrastructure, whether in an NFV-MANO or Kubernetes environment.

Additionally, the Security Orchestrator can enforce predefined security and privacy policies by instructing the NMTD to apply updates, triggering the necessary configuration changes. If the risk (or privacy) score exceeds an acceptable threshold, indicating a security (or privacy) risk, the Security Orchestrator can either request the termination of the service or enforce new policies to mitigate the risk.

The following figure illustrates this workflow in a sequence diagram.

Figure 10 - Workflow of the Onboarding, DevSecOps and DevPrivOps processes

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Onboarding Tools are summarized in the following table.

Table 4 Details on Onboarding Tools

OT - Onboarding Tools		
Capabilities	Onboard services and policies in the Security Orchestrator.	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	Security Orchestrator	
Interfaces	nOT_OnboardingTools	
	Description	This interface allows the Security Orchestrator to receive the onboarded services and respective policies.
	From Provider	OT
	To Consumer	Security Orchestrator

5.4.2. Security Orchestration and Enforcement

The orchestration and enforcement processes provide a way to deploy and enforce security policies under demand to the different enablers in the RIGOUROUS architecture. This process starts with the Decision Engine component generating and sending a MSPL policy to the Security Orchestrator, as a result of a decision taken after detecting an anomaly or event. The Security Orchestrator checks for any conflict between the new policy received and the already deployed policies with the Intent Security Manager. This component obtains a list with all the deployed policies from the Policy Repository, and analyzes any conflicts with the new policy to be applied. The result is sent to the Security Orchestrator, which stops the process if any conflict has been detected, or continue requesting a MSPL translation to the Intent Security Manager if not. The Intent Security Manager contains different modules that are configured to translate policies in MSPL language to the correspondent configuration messages for every supported enabler. After that, the Security Orchestrator obtains the endpoints that correspond to the targeted enablers and checks if the related services are running from the Data Services component. If the required services are up and running, the Security Orchestrator then obtains the information about the security enablers from the Security Enablers Provider. This information will be used in the allocation process, in which the Security Orchestrator generates a plan with all the resources that are needed to apply the policy. Finally, the Security Orchestrator delivers the configuration message to the correspondent driver, that is in charge of deploy the configuration into the enabler. This workflow is represented in the following figure.

Figure 11 - Workflow of the Security Orchestrator processes

Table 5 Details on Security Orchestrator

SO - Security Orchestrator	
Capabilities	Process MSPL policies to create and deploy specific enabler configurations.
Visibility	Internal / External.

Potential Consumers	Security enablers	
Interfaces	nSO_SecPolEnforc	
	Description	This interface allows the decision engine to send a decision about a security plan to be enforced on the infrastructure through the Security Orchestrator.
	From Provider	Decision Engine
	To Consumer	Security Orchestrator
	nISM_DetConf	
	Description	This interface allows the AI-driven Security Orchestrator to identify conflicts in a set of orchestration policies. The input will be a set of policies to be checked against conflicts and the output will be a set of triplets, each one indicating the pair of policies causing the conflict and the conflict type.
	From Provider	Security Orchestrator
	To Consumer	Intent Security Manager
	nISM_TransMSPL	
	Description	This interface allows the Orchestrator to refine and translate the security policies received in MSPL format into low level configurations to be enforced on the system/network.
	From Provider	Security Orchestrator
	To Consumer	Intent Security Manager
	nSA_SecLocEnforc	
	Description	This interface allows the Orchestrator to communicate with Security agents to enforce on them a security policy. Different Security agents will require specific data models and APIs for their configurations (depending on its implementation).
	From Provider	Security Orchestrator
To Consumer	Security Agent	

5.4.3 Zero Trust

Zero Trust is achieved in the RIGOUROUS architecture following the principle of *never trust, always verify*. The Zero Trust management assumes no implicit trust in the network and continuously analyses and evaluates the risks to the network assets/resources. Some of the primary assets/resources in a communication network can include radio access network entities, core network functions, application functions, data storage/management network functions, operation and management functions etc., In Zero Trust, the protections usually involve minimizing access to resources (e.g., data and services) to only those subjects and assets requesting access by considering the authentication, authorization and security posture of the requestor (i.e., including the behavioural statistics, reported threats/attacks etc.). Existing authentication methods used in 5G system/5G-advanced system (e.g., TLS used in SBA security and IP sec used for Non-SBA security)

and Authorization aspects (e.g., OAuth based access tokens) can be reused for the 6G network security, but that is not sufficient. If any network resource/asset is compromised, it can lead to lateral movement of the attack. The existing authentication mechanisms can help to verify identity authentication, and authorization can help to enforce access restrictions based on OAuth access token, but none of the existing mechanism helps to identify the risk associated to the compromised network asset/resource. Therefore, the Zero Trust Management function offered by the RIGOUROUS Framework proposes event (e.g., abnormal behaviour) based data collection and exposure to enable security risk/threat identification by Operator's security evaluation/monitoring. Aligned to the High level architecture of RIGOUROUS, the ZTM component has 2 major functionalities: NF log analysis and trust score assignment and notification.

Table 6 Details on Zero Trust Management

ZTM - Zero Trust Management Service		
Capabilities	Notify anomaly and trust score to service consumer.	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-driven Decision Engine • Security Orchestrator 	
Interfaces	nZTM_ZeroTrustManagement	
	Description	This interface allows the AI-driven Decision Engine to be notified about occurrence of anomalies and trust scores.
	From Provider	ZTM
	To Consumer	AI-driven Decision Engine

Figure 12 - Workflows of the Zero Trust Management

5.4.4 6G Network Slicing

Network slicing in 5G and 6G infrastructures enables the creation of multiple virtualized logical networks over a shared physical infrastructure. These network slices provide isolated end-to-end (E2E) networks for specific use cases, ensuring different Quality of Service (QoS) levels as required. In this section, we present a set of components within the RIGOUROUS framework that, when integrated, enable an automated response and mitigation service against cyberattacks. This service leverages the advantages of network slicing in 5G/6G infrastructures to dynamically protect both physical and virtual network devices.

The scenario analysed in this section begins with a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack orchestrated by a swarm of authenticated 5G/6G User Equipment (UE) within the network. The target of the attack is an internet-based entity located at the far end of the infrastructure. During the attack, some UEs continue generating legitimate network traffic. The goal of our mitigation strategy is to isolate and neutralize malicious traffic by dynamically creating a dedicated E2E network slice for each infected UE while ensuring that legitimate traffic remains unaffected.

Aligned with the RIGOUROUS High-Level Architecture (HLA), this scenario involves three key functional blocks:

- Data Monitoring, responsible for collecting network flow and topology information.
- Decision Making & Mitigation, which determines and enforces mitigation strategies.
- Reaction Plane & 6G Infrastructure, where data plane enablers implement the mitigation actions.

Figure 13 illustrates the workflow of this scenario, from the detection of the cyberattack to its mitigation.

The Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) continuously updates the 5G/6G topology, reporting changes in both physical and virtual resources, such as interfaces, Virtual Machines (VMs), virtual bridges, and switches (see steps 1-3 in Figure 13). Simultaneously, the Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM) system passively monitors mirrored network traffic and triggers an alert when detects a DDoS attack. This alert is published to the message bus exchange and consumed by the Slicing Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS) (see steps 5-7 in Figure 13).

When receives an attack alert, the SMPS correlates 5G/6G network flow data with topology information to reconstruct the E2E path of the malicious traffic. It then applies prescriptive analytics techniques to determine the optimal mitigation strategy, specifying what action to take, where to apply the actions, when must the actions be applied and for how long these actions should be applied. The mitigation plan is then published via the Security Orchestrator (SO) API (see steps 4, 8, and 9 in Figure 13).

The SO manages the E2E mitigation process within the 5G/6G network data plane, coordinating with the Slice Manager (SM) and Network Self-Protection (NSP) components. These two elements enable technology-agnostic network slicing within the data plane. Initially, the SO instructs the SM to create and configure the required network slice. This configuration is then propagated to the NSP, which is distributed across the entire 5G/6G control plane and leverages Open vSwitch (OVS) technology. Upon successful slice configuration, the NSP acknowledges the SM and SO. The SO then instructs the system to associate the identified malicious flow with the newly created slice (see steps 10-21 in Figure 13).

Once all mitigation points have been addressed, the system successfully isolates the attack while preserving legitimate network activity, achieving the desired security outcome.

Figure 13 - Workflow of the 6G Network Slicing process

5.4.5. AI-based anomaly detection

5.4.5.1 Function

The AI-driven Security Analytics Engine (AI-SAE) derives insights and predictions of a domain's security conditions based on data collected inside the domain or from other domains. The SAE provides different services, including the Anomaly Detection service, the Federated Training service, the Privacy-Enhancing service, the MTD service, and the Cyber Physical Correlator service. The *Anomaly Detection service* is an AI-powered service that possesses the capabilities to detect

and/or predict abnormal behaviour resulting from either malicious or unintentional actions. It achieves this by identifying patterns in data or behaviour that deviate from the expected normal behaviour. It leverages data collected by the Data Monitoring functional block from managed entities within the domain, including performance and security monitoring data, events and alarms, generated by system logs and packet traces. Once an anomaly is detected, the AI-driven Decision functional block is notified, providing necessary information that can help in determining the nature of the cyber threat or intrusion causing the anomaly. The *Federated Training service* enables for training the ML models integrated in the Anomaly Detection service in a collaborative way using the concept of Federated Learning, which allows knowledge sharing between SAEs of different domains without exchanging domain's local data. The *Privacy-Enhancing service* offers various Privacy-Enhancing Techniques (PETs) (e.g., Homomorphic encryption and Differential Privacy) that can be applied to foster the privacy-preservation of the FL process. The *MTD service* has the capability of protecting the ML models involved in the Anomaly Detection service against adversarial attacks by applying a moving target defense strategy. Finally, the *Cyber Physical Correlator service* is a service that uses Machine Learning algorithms to detect and mitigate anomalies and cyber-threats, both external and internal. The threats are identified by monitoring the traffic flow of the network and detecting behaviours that are not compatible with normal functioning. When a threat is identified, Cyber Physical Correlator notifies AI-driven Decision to proceed with further analysis of the incident.

5.4.5.2 Provided services

The following figure depicts the different services and interfaces provided by the AI-driven Security Analytics functional block of RIGOUROUS framework.

Figure 14 - Services and Interfaces of AI-driven Security Analytics Engine

A. Anomaly Detection Service

This service has the capabilities of detecting and/or predicting anomalous behaviours resulting from malicious or accidental actions. The service can ingest time series data of different types, including security alarms, performance, and usage metrics that could be collected by the Data Monitoring at different layers (e.g., network layer, application layer). The anomaly detection is performed using an ML model trained following a federated learning process to enable knowledge sharing for increased anomaly detection accuracy without sharing local data. Upon detecting anomalies, the AI-driven Decision Engine is notified to make well-informed decision concerning the nature of cyber threat or intrusion behind the detected anomalies.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Anomaly Detection Service are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7 Details on Anomaly Detection Service

AI-SAE - Anomaly Detection Service	
Capabilities	Notify anomaly to service consumer.
Visibility	Internal / External.

Potential Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-driven Decision Engine • Data Services 	
Interfaces	nSAE_AnomalyDetection	
	Description	This interface allows the AI-driven Decision Engine to be notified about occurrence of anomalies.
	From Provider	AI-SAE
	To Consumer	AI-driven Decision Engine

The following figure illustrates the workflow of detecting network anomalies using the Anomaly Detection Service.

Figure 14 - Workflow of network anomaly detection using Anomaly Detection Service

B. Federated Training Service

This service enables the consumer to subscribe and get notified for the training of anomaly detection ML model through a FL process. It involves Security Agents from the infrastructure plane acting as FL agents and aggregators. These work collaboratively to perform the FL training through an iterative exchange of previously protected model updates. The local ML models are trained on the FL Agent's local data for each round. That data has been previously collected from the network (in a training phase controlled mode). The FL training is repeated until the training termination condition (e.g., maximum number of training rounds) is reached. Upon finishing the FL training, the new trained ML model can be used to replace the current ML model integrated in the Anomaly Detection Service.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Federated Training Service are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8 Details on Federated Training Service

AI-SAE - Federated Training Service		
Capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscribe the training request by a service consumer. • Notify the consumer of the trained model. 	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-SAE 	
Interfaces	nSAE_FederatedTraining	
	Description	This interface allows its consumer to subscribe and get notified for FL training of anomaly detection ML model.
	From Provider	AI-SAE
	To Consumer	AI-SAE

The following figure illustrates the workflow of training traffic collection, processing, and Federated Learning-based training using the Federated Training service.

Figure 15 - Workflow of Federated Learning training using Federated Training Service

C. Privacy-Enhancing Service

This service provides a set of privacy-enhancing techniques (PETs) that could be leveraged by the Federated Training service to enable privacy-preserving FL training process, aiming to prevent potential inference attacks. The provided PETs include Homomorphic Encryption (HE) and

Differential Privacy (DP). The HE method allows the model aggregation to be performed on encrypted local model updates, while DP applies noises on the exchanged local model updates.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Privacy-Enhancing Service are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9 Details on Privacy-Enhancing Service

AI-SAE - Privacy-Enhancing Service		
Capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Encrypt/Decrypt local ML model parameters.• Apply DP noise on local ML model parameters.	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	AI-SAE	
Interfaces	nSAE_PrivacyEnhancing	
	Description	This interface allows its consumer to apply an implemented PET to enable privacy-preserving FL training.
	From Provider	AI-SAE
	To Consumer	AI-SAE

The following figure illustrates the workflow of privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detection training, leveraging the homomorphic encryption capability of the Privacy-Enhancing Service.

Figure 16 - Workflow of privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detection training using Privacy-Enhancing Service

D. MTD Service

This service provides a MTD strategy that allows to prevent adversarial attacks against ML models. The MTD strategy could consist in strategically and dynamically selecting a ML model among a pool of ML models trained for achieving the same learning task (e.g., anomaly detection). By doing so, it becomes difficult for the attacker to launch an adversarial attack.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the MTD Service are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10 Details on MTD Service

AI-SAE - MTD Service		
Capabilities	Select ML model to use for the learning task.	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-SAE Any functional block integrating ML models 	
Interfaces	nSAE_MTD	
	Description	This interface allows its consumer to select to dynamically select a ML model to use for inference from a pool of trained ML models following an MTD strategy.
	From Provider	AI-SAE

	To Consumer	Any functional block integrating ML models including AI-SAE
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The following Figure illustrates the workflow of using MTD Service to enable robust AI-based anomaly detection.

Figure 17 - Workflow of MTD Service

E. Cyber Physical Correlator Service

This service has the capabilities of detecting security breach. More specifically, it can monitor network traffic flow and in case of an anomaly detection, send a corresponding message. For the detection, several ML models are used. Some of the features that are used for the training are Source IP address, Source port number, Destination IP address, Destination port number, Transaction protocol, Record total duration, Source to destination transaction bytes, Destination to source transaction bytes, Source to destination time to live value, Destination to source time to live value, Source packets retransmitted or dropped, Destination packets retransmitted or dropped, Source bits per second etc.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Cyber Physical Correlator Service are summarized in Table 11.

Table 11 Details on Cyber Physical Correlator Service

AI-SAE - Cyber Physical Correlator Service	
Capabilities	Detect security breach by monitoring the traffic flow.
Visibility	Internal / External.

Potential Consumers	AI-driven Decision Engine	
Interfaces	AID-CPC	
	Description	This interface allows Correlator, which can detect anomalies in network, to notify AI-driven Decision Engine about the identified anomaly and give specific information about the reasons that caused the alert.
	From Provider	AI-SAE
	To Consumer	AI-driven Decision Engine

Figure 18 illustrates the workflow of using CPC Service to enable robust AI-based anomaly detection.

Figure 18 - Workflow of CPC analysing traffic and producing/transmitting threats to AID

5.7.6. AI-based Decision

Table 12 Details on AID Service

AID - AI based decision		
Capabilities	Proposed mitigation action against threats	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	Security orchestrators (SO)	
Interfaces	AID-SO	
	Description	The interface allows the AID to provide proposed mitigation actions to security orchestrator

	From Provider	AID
	To Consumer	security orchestrator

AID - AI based decision		
Capabilities	use ML algorithm to formulate the optimum response to the received threats from the anomaly detections assets	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	Internal to the AI-RM module	
Interfaces	AID-R12/AID-CPC/AID-ZTM	
	Description	The interfaces allows the AID to receive anomalies from the different anomaly detection engine within the toolkit (R12, ZTM and CPT) to formulate the optimum response
	From Provider	R12/CPC/ZTM
	To Consumer	AI-RM module of the AID

AID - AI based decision		
Capabilities	Map and integrate the risk score for the received anomalies from a different engine (TRA) to better formulate the response	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	Internal to the AID module	
Interfaces	AID-TRA	
	Description	The interfaces allows the AID to receive the risk score for the anomalies detected by anomaly detection assets (R12/CPC and ZTM) and correlate each score to the appropriate anomaly and formulate a more precise response action
	From Provider	TRA
	To Consumer	AID internal engine

In terms of building block that interact with the AID, we can find below in the following figure, all the active interfaces active during the operation mode

Figure 7 - Building blocks AID decision

Kafka serves as a central hub between the AID and all surrounding modules, facilitating seamless message exchange. Messages are either produced and published to the relevant Kafka topic or consumed and retrieved from it.

The sequence of message exchanges within this communication is illustrated in Figure below.

Figure 8 - AID sequence diagram

Within the anomaly detection process, three distinct stages can be identified, each represented by different colors.

Stage 1: Anomaly Detection Initiation

Referred to as "Anomaly Detectors" in the sequence diagram, this stage involves multiple modules that continuously monitor network activity to detect irregularities. The detection workflow operates across two primary planes:

- The first plane encompasses all three R12 modules, which collectively identify anomalies in network traffic and security events.
- The second plane is associated with the R08 module, which follows a distinct detection and assessment methodology.

The anomaly detection process is triggered when either R12 or R08 identifies suspicious activity.

- R12 Modules: Upon detecting an anomaly, R12 generates an attack log using the STIX (Structured Threat Information Expression) format, ensuring a standardized and structured representation of cyber threats. This log captures essential details, such as the type of anomaly, affected assets, and metadata.
- The attack log is published to Kafka topic R12-TRA-AID (Topic 1 in Fig. 22).
- TRA (R19) retrieves this log and conducts a severity assessment, assigning a risk score that quantifies the potential impact.
- The computed risk score is then published to Kafka topic TRA-AID (Topic 2 in Fig. 22) for further processing.
- AID (R16) consumes the risk score and cross-references it with the anomaly ID obtained from Topic 1 to determine the most appropriate course of action.
- Based on this analysis, AID formulates an optimal mitigation strategy and transmits it to SO (R07) for execution.

Stage 2: Trust-Based Anomaly Assessment

At this stage, the Zero Trust Model (ZTM) ensures that security threats are assessed with a focus on mitigating risks such as unauthorized access, lateral movement of threats, and potential service disruptions.

- The ZTM (R08) module evaluates the trustworthiness of network entities, including Physical and Virtual Network Functions (PNFs and VNFs), RAN and Core infrastructure, application functions, and end-user devices.
- If an anomaly is detected, R08 generates a risk assessment and publishes it to Kafka topic R08-AID, along with a trust-based risk score.
- Unlike Stage 1, TRA (R19) is not involved in this phase.
- AID (R16) consumes the anomaly data and risk score from R08-AID, evaluates the implications, and determines an appropriate response.
- The mitigation action is then sent to SO (R07), ensuring that security orchestration aligns with trust-based risk evaluations.

Stage 3: Execution of Mitigation Actions

At the final stage, SO (R07) takes control of the response process, executing the mitigation strategies defined by AID (R16). The objective is to swiftly neutralize threats and prevent anomalies from escalating into full-scale security breaches.

- Upon receiving mitigation instructions from AID, SO directly interacts with the network infrastructure to implement security measures in real time.
- These actions may include network reconfigurations, access control modifications, deployment of countermeasures, or isolation of compromised assets.
- By acting immediately on validated risk assessments, SO ensures the integrity, security, and resilience of the network, preventing potential intrusions from penetrating deeper into critical systems.

By integrating risk-based scoring (Stage 1), trust-based evaluation (Stage 2), and direct intervention (Stage 3), this anomaly detection framework enhances security through proactive threat mitigation, real-time response, and optimized network protection

5.4.7. Risk Assessment

Table 13 Details on TRA Service

RTA Service	
Capabilities	Assign a threat risk score associated to a threat/anomaly concerning one or more assets in the network.

Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	AID, OT, NMTD	
Interfaces	nTRA_Risk_Score_Engine	
	Description	Even though this interface emphasizes the AID, any interested functional block can use the same interface for consuming the threat risk scores provided by it.
	From Provider	TRA
	To Consumer	Any other functional block interested in the information contained in the risk score data structure.

Figure 9 - Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) Processing

1) Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) Processing

- The Risk Score Engine within the TRA (R19) retrieves the attack log from Topic R12-TRA-AID.
- It deserializes the log, extracting the primary key (PK) to identify the affected asset.
- The System Model is queried to determine the Asset ID corresponding to the anomaly.
- Once the Asset ID is obtained, the TRA queries the CVE Database (CVE DB) to retrieve vulnerability information related to the affected asset.
- The TRA analyzes the anomaly and vulnerability data, assessing the severity of the threat based on an internal risk matrix and external contextual factors.

2) Risk Score Publication & Mitigation Strategy

- The computed risk score is published to Kafka Topic TRA-AID for further processing. which is then mainly consumed by the AID (R16) or potentially other components which might be interested in such information.

5.4.8 Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin

The Dynamic Automated Service Composition (DASC) works alongside the Digital Twin (DT) to address mismatches or misconfigurations and the security threats that arise from them. Such mismatches and misconfigurations comprise:

- Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities require adapters or converters, which can introduce security loopholes.
- Incompatible data formats can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data.
- Organizations may struggle to enforce uniform security policies across diverse systems, leading to misconfigurations.

The DT emulates system behaviours and simulates the network traffic flow, so as to ensure that mismatches and associated security threats can be identified before they happen. It acts as a security testing/validation tool, in order to help verify that different system components can communicate effectively under various conditions. When a mismatch is detected from the DASC, it proposes repairing mechanisms (e.g. reconfiguration to adapt affected components, modifying service parameters, updating protocol translations) in the corresponding components. These repairing actions are sent as mitigation plan to the Response-Mitigation (RM) to enforce the mitigation. Then, the Response-Mitigation Service of the RM component applies the mitigation action on the system by contacting its associated security agents and managers.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin Services are summarized in Table KK.

Table 14 Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin Services

Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin Services	
Capabilities	Emulate system behaviours and network traffic, so as to detect mismatches/configurations and associated security threats before they happen.
Visibility	Internal / External.
Potential Consumers	Response-Mitigation (RM)
Interfaces	DT-DSC-AI_RM
	Description This interface allows Automated Service Composition, which can detect mismatches or misconfigurations in network, to notify the Response and Mitigation about

		the required repair actions to be enforced as mitigation plan to the associated security agents and managers.
	From Provider	Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin
	To Consumer	Response Mitigation

Figure 10 - Workflow of interaction between Digital twin and Dynamic Service composition

5.4.9 Response and Mitigation

5.4.9.1 Function

The RIGOROUS Response Mitigation (RM) functional block main role is to act enforce mitigation strategies directly into the managed system to successfully mitigation cyber attacks. The functional block currently provides the following services:

- 1) Slice Control Service: its main role is to enforce in the dataplane controlled under the scope of such service, the quality of service requirements to achieve network slicing (performance isolation) in such dataplane.
- 2) AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service: it exploits the potential of Deep Learning to automatically discriminate malicious resource scaling requests engendered by application-layer DDoS attacks from those caused by legitimate load.

5.4.9.2 Provided Services

A. Slice Control Service

The Slice Control Service is a critical component for traffic classification and control in 5G/6G multi-tenant networks, particularly in the software data path segment. This service is provided by the Network Self-Protection (NSP) asset in the RIGOUROUS framework, which enhances network slicing for cyber-attack mitigation.

Key Features of the NSP:

- **Traffic Classification & Security:** The NSP offers a novel traffic classifier that enables deep packet inspection (DPI) for identifying user, service, and SLA-based traffic in multi-tenant environments.
- **Enhanced OpenFlow API:** Extends OpenFlow protocol for improved flow definition and network slicing control.
- **Multi-tenancy Support:** Capable of handling virtualized overlay networks with complex tunnelling protocols (e.g., GTP, VXLAN, GRE, GENEVE).
- **Modular & Efficient Architecture:** Features re-entrant modules to optimize parsing time and enhance flexibility.

NSP Sub-components:

- **OpenFlow NBI:** Connects the Control Plane (Slice Manager) to the Software Data Plane, exposing an enhanced OpenFlow API.
- **5G/6G Multi-tenant Traffic Classifier:** Conducts deep packet inspection and extracts an extended flow key for precise traffic identification.
- **Slice Definition Table:** Defines network slices using OpenFlow rules, linking flows to specific slices.
- **Match Flow Action:** Matches incoming traffic against slice definitions for enforcement.
- **Actions and Slice Enforcer:** Applies network slicing actions before forwarding packets.
- **Network Slicing Core:** Enforces slice policies on physical/virtual network interfaces, ensuring proper resource allocation.

The main application of this asset is explained in Section 5.4.4, with the rest of functionalities and assets involved in the 6G Network Slicing Service. Additionally, following figure depicts the NSP architecture with the connections of its subcomponents.

Figure 11 - Architecture of NSP asset in the RIGUROUS framework

B. AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service

The service prevents an undetected application-layer DDoS attack against a network slice's VNF to reshape into an EDoS attack, exploiting the auto-scaling capability. To this end, the service leverages the potential of DL to automatically discriminate malicious resource scaling requests engendered by application-layer DDoS attacks from those caused by legitimate load. It includes a DL-based anomaly detection model which can effectively identify anomalous CNFs' metrics using a data-driven forecasting-based approach. Indeed, the anomalies are detected when the predicted metrics' values drift considerably from the observed ones. If an anomaly is identified, the scaling operation is flagged as malicious and will be refused. The AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service may notify the AI-driven Decision Engine on malicious scaling operations in order to trigger further measures to mitigate the attack, such as analysing network traffic by AI-SAE to identify the source of the attack.

Details on the capabilities, visibility, potential consumers, and interfaces of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service are summarized in the following table

Table 15 Details on AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service

RM - AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service		
Capabilities	Allow/Prevent resource scaling operation	
Visibility	Internal / External.	
Potential Consumers	Auto-Scaling Service	
Interfaces	nRM_EDoSMitigation	
	Description	This interface allows the auto-scaling service to entrust the resource scaling decision to AI-powered EDoS Mitigation service for validation.
	From Provider	RM
	To Consumer	Auto-Scaling Service

Next figure illustrates the workflow of assessing the legitimacy/maliciousness of the resource scaling request by the AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service.

Figure 12 - Workflow of AI-powered EDoS Mitigation Service

6 MAPPING OF RIGOUROUS TO STANDARDS

6.1 ETSI ZSM

The Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) architecture from ETSI describes a set of architectural principles for a zero-touch automated network and service management in a multi-vendor environment where SOAR can be applied for the management of envisioned 6G networks. It is based on 13 principles [1], Modularity, Extensibility, Scalability, Model-driven, closed-loop management, stateless management, resilience, separation of concerns, service composability, intent-based interfaces, functional abstraction, simplicity, automation.

These principles are materialized in a set of general functional requirements in the ZSM architecture that are inherit in RIGOUROUS. Nonetheless, ZSM is mainly focused on service management and different security principles raised from the fact of adopting a SOAR approach for security management are not directly considered in the architecture.

ZSM follows the OODA loop “Observe, Orient, Decide, Act” steps [6] to or MAPE-K (Monitor-Analyse-Plan-Execute plus Knowledge [7]) or MRACL (Model-Reference Adaptive Control Loop [8]).

As stated in [1], to achieve closed-loop operation, a management framework needs to provide means for the ordered invocation of the steps or phases of the closed loop, the composition of the necessary functionalities (i.e., composition of management services and functions) at each step of the closed loop, and the transfer of, and access to necessary information between the steps of the closed loop.

RIGOUROUS expands ZSM Management with a set of dedicated security functional components for cognitive security decision, security management, supporting SOAR closed-loop operation specially focused on security matters:

- AI-driven Decision Maker (AID)
- Zero Trust and Identity Management (ZTM)
- Security Orchestrator (SO)
- The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)
- Intent-Based Security Management (ISM):
- Digital Twin (DT)
- Automatic Service Composition (ASC)
- Response-Mitigation (RM)

The following figure shows the ZSM architecture

Figure 13 ETSI ZSM architecture [1]

The following table provides the mapping between Rigorous architectural components described previously and ZSM functions. The Rigorous components can be mapped to the Management Functions plane of ZSM, either within a single domain or multi-domain (E2E).

Table 16 Mapping between Rigorous and ZSM

RIGOUROUS component	Provided ZSM services
E2E SAE (Security Analytics Engine): performs federated AI training for multi-domain scenarios	E2E Analytics
E2E Security Orchestrator: Distribute and enforce policies in the different domains	E2E orchestration E2E Data services
E2E AID: Make decisions about security E2E policies to enforce in multi-domain scenarios	E2E Domain intelligence

E2E ISM: Validate and refine policies	Supporting services
Security Orchestrator	Domain orchestration
Intent Based Security management (ISM): Translate policies in domain	Domain orchestration Domain control Domain data services
Decision Engine: Create security plan for mitigations	Domain intelligence
Security Analytics Engine (SAE): Detect attacks and anomalies using AI	Domain intelligence
pp-CTI: retrieves and manages CTI information	Domain intelligence
Data monitoring (DM): Collect security data from infrastructure & Monitoring and topology Agents	Domain data collection
Monitoring Agents (MA): Different assets to provide data, aggregate info generates security alerts	Domain data collection Domain data analytics Domain intelligence
Security Agents (SA): security enablers such as virtual firewall to actuate and response on the network	Domain Control
Zero Trust (ZTM): dynamic trust evaluation of entities, and services	Domain intelligence
Response Mitigation (RM): applies sophisticated real-time responses to mitigate attacks	Domain control, domain intelligence
Threat Risk Assessor (TRA): computes risk scores about entities	Domain intelligence
Digital Twin (DT): simulate networks to validate deployments	Domain operations
Dynamic Automated Service Composition (DSC): detects and resolves interconnection issues among components, addressing protocol mismatches	Domain control, Domain intelligence
MANO stack: NFVO (Open Source MANO) + VIM (Openstack + k8s) + SDN controller	Domain orchestration Domain control
Integration Fabric	Mgmt. Service Discovery Mgmt. Communication

6.2 3GPP

The concepts related to Zero Trust Management such as various abnormal behaviour data collection aspects for Trust/security evaluation and monitoring aspects has been significantly contributed, and most of them were approved in 3GPP Release 18 and Release 19 Technical Reports as listed below. Some of the key 3GPP contributions made by RIGOUROUS partner Lenovo related to the concept of ZTM is listed. Detailed 3GPP contribution information was also reported in the M6, M12, M18 and M24 per partner Technical report and periodic SNS reporting activities respectively.

1. Rel.18 3GPP TR 33.894, 'Study on applicability of the zero trust security principles in mobile networks'.

Available for Ref: [HTTPS://WWW.3GPP.ORG/FTP/SPECS/ARCHIVE/33_SERIES/33.894/33894-I00.ZIP](https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/specs/archive/33_series/33.894/33894-I00.zip)

2. Rel.19 3GPP TR 33.794, ' Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security'.

Available for Ref: [HTTPS://WWW.3GPP.ORG/FTP/SPECS/ARCHIVE/33_SERIES/33.794/33794-J00.ZIP](https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/specs/archive/33_series/33.794/33794-J00.zip)

Following standards contributions were made to the 3GPP Security WG.

1. S3-234224: Add Tenets to Tenet Evaluation Summary
2. S3-234200: Data collection for Security Monitoring
3. S3-234201: Conclusion to KI#1
4. S3-234204: Update to Tenet #7
5. S3-234416: Discussions for Rel-19 Study on enablers for ZTS
6. S3-235089: New SID on enablers for Zero Trust Security
7. S3-240896: Draft TR33.794 Skeleton
8. S3-240897: Scope to TR 33.794
9. S3-240898: Security Assumptions for TR 33.794
10. S3-240903: Data related to Malformed Message
11. S3-240904: Data related to Massive number of Service Messages
12. S3-241004: Use case: security data exposure for API security risks on 5G SBA layer
13. S3-241005: KI related to WT1
14. S3-241021: Usecase for security policy enforcement
15. S3-241137: Updates to Access control decision enhancement usecase
16. S3-241525: Adding requirements to KI#1 "Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring"
17. S3-241526: Adding Key Issue on WT2 "Security mechanism for dynamic policy enforcement"
18. S3-241527: Update of the security assumptions
19. S3-241537: Resolve EN and provide updates to use case 3
20. S3-241538: Resolve EN and provide updates to use case 4

21. S3-241568: Updates to Massive number of SBI messages
22. S3-241570: Updates to Malformed Message Usecase
23. S3-242420: Updates to evaluation on massive number of calls use case
24. S3-242418: Resolve EN in Use case 1
25. S3-242423: Updates to eZTS Key Issue 2
26. S3-242424: Solution to KI#1 Network assisted data collection
27. S3-242425: Solution to KI#1_Direct data collection
28. S3-243496: Updates to Solution #2
29. S3-243505: Initial Conclusion to KI#1
30. S3-243611: Solution to KI#2
31. S3-243845: KI#1 Conclusion Update
32. S3-243846: Solution#1 assumptions clarification
33. S3-243848: KI#2 Initial Conclusion
34. S3-244251: New WID on enablers for Zero Trust Security
35. S3-244332: Solution#9 Update
36. S3-244335: Conclusion for Key Issue #2 "Security mechanisms for policy enforcement at the 5G SBA"
37. S3-244327: eZTS KI 1 Conclusions
38. S3-245182: Updates and Clean-up of KI#1 Conclusion

7 CONCLUSIONS

This document has described the final Rigorous architecture including its main proactive and reactive process workflows. In particular, additional architectural workflows have been described for the following functional processes being devised in Rigorous: Onboarding, Devsecops, Security Orchestration and Enforcement, Zero Trust, 6G Network Slicing, Ai-Based Anomaly Detection, Ai-Based Decision, Risk Assessment, Automated Service Composition and Digital Twin and Response And Mitigation.

That architecture it is currently being further developed to satisfy the detailed and updated process workflows presented in this document. The process workflows definitions have been designed considering the research activities being tackled in WP3, WP4 and WP5, and also bearing in mind the demands from requirements and use case descriptions.

The section about mapping of Rigorous to standards have been introduced to facilitate the further adoption and uptake of Rigorous in the future. It shows the alignment and compliance of Rigorous architecture with ongoing standardization activities.

Moreover, this document has defined an updated version of Rigours requirements that now describes in more detail the expected Rigorous functionality. The requirements have been updated considering the experience gathered so far in the project by the partners . Finally, the use cases have been also streamlined to include more realistic threat scenarios, attacks and associated mitigations supported in Rigorous.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM), "ETSI GS ZSM 002 V1.1.1", August 2019
- [2] NIST SP 800-160v1r1, [Online], <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.800-160v1r1.pdf>, [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [3] MITRE Systems Engineering Guide, [Online], <https://www.mitre.org/sites/default/files/2022-09/MITRE-SEG.pdf>, [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [4] VOLERE Requirements Resources, [Online], <https://www.volere.org/templates/volere-requirements-specification-template/> [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [5] Market Guide for Security Orchestration, Automation and Response Solutions, [Online], <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/security-orchestration-automation-response-market-176584778.html> [Accessed 8 Sept 2023]
- [6] Boyd, J.R.: "The Essence of Winning and Losing", June 1995.
- [7] Kephart, J. and D. Chess: "The Vision of Autonomic Computing", IEEE Computer, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 41-50, DOI 10.1109/MC.2003.1160055, January 2003.
- [8] Miller, D.E.: "A new approach to model reference adaptive control", IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control, Volume: 48, Issue: 5, May 2003.
- [9] Rapid7 Documentation, [Online], <https://docs.rapid7.com/>, [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [10] FireEye Documentation, [Online], <https://fireeye.com/dev/docs/helix/>, [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [11] Palo Alto Documentation, [Online], <https://www.paloaltonetworks.com/cortex/cortex-xsoar>, [Accessed 24 August 2023]
- [12] A. Khraisat, I. Gondal, P. Vamplew, and J. Kamruzzaman, "Survey of intrusion detection systems: techniques, datasets and challenges," Cybersecurity, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 20, Jul 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42400-019-0038-7>
- [13] E. M. Campos, P. F. Saura, A. González-Vidal, J. L. Hernández-Ramos, J. B. Bernabé, G. Baldini, and A. Skarmeta, "Evaluating federated learning for intrusion detection in internet of things: Review and challenges," Computer Networks, vol. 203, p. 108661, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128621005405>
- [14] J. Pei, K. Zhong, M. A. Jan, and J. Li, "Retracted: Personalized federated learning framework for network traffic anomaly detection," Computer Networks, vol. 209, p. 108906, 2022. [Online], <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128622001001> [Accessed 18 July 2023]
- [15] O. A. Wahab, A. Mourad, H. Otok, and T. Taleb, "Federated machine learning: Survey, multi-level classification, desirable criteria and future directions in communication and networking systems," IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1342-1397, 2021.
- [16] Tovima.com, [Online], <https://www.tovima.com/climate/clean-energy-powers-over-half-of-greeces-electricity-demand/>

[17] Cyberattack on Vodafone [Online]. [HTTPS://WWW.VODAFONE.PT/EN/PRESS-RELEASES/2022/2/CYBERATTACK-ON-VODAFONE-PORTUGAL.HTML](https://www.vodafone.pt/en/press-releases/2022/2/cyberattack-on-vodafone-portugal.html))

[18] Rigorous deliverable D2.1 - “System Requirements Analysis Report”, Sept.2023